

**A PROSPECTIVE STUDY OF FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF
INTERTROCHANTERIC FRACTURES TREATED WITH
TROCHANTERIC FEMORAL NAIL.**

By

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Dissertation submitted to

In partial fulfillment for the degree of

MASTER OF SURGERY

IN

ORTHOPAEDICS

Under the guidance of

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2018

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

On completion of my post graduation journey and this scientific document, I would like to acknowledge the immense help received from my mentors in the Department of Orthopaedics.

*With privilege and respect I would like to express my gratitude and indebtedness to my Guide and HOD, **Dr. O.B. Pattanashetty**, for his constant inspiration, extensive encouragement and loving support, which he rendered in pursuit of my post-graduate studies and in preparing this dissertation.*

*I am forever grateful to Professors **Dr. A.R. Nayak** and **Dr. S.S. Nandi** for their guidance and encouragement provided to me, to achieve new heights professionally over my course period.*

*I am grateful to Associate Prof. **Dr. Dayanand B.B.** and **Dr. Ramanagouda Biradar** for their guidance, encouragement and inspiration.*

I am thankful to Dr. Girish K, Dr. Sandeep Naik, Dr. Rajakumar Bagewadi, Dr. Srikant, Dr. Vinaykumar Babaleshwar, Dr. Anil Bulgond, Dr. Sreepad K for their great help.

I am extremely thankful to Prof. Dr. S. P. Guggarigoudar, Principal, of B.L.D.E.U'S Shri. B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, VIJAYAPUR, for permitting me to utilize resources in completion of my work.

My thanks to one and all staff of Library, Orthopaedics Department and Hospital for their co-operation in my study.

I am thankful to my seniors, Dr. Aravind, Dr. Ullas, Dr. Sridhar, for their advice, suggestions and co-operation in my journey.

I would also like to thank my colleagues Dr. Sharad, Dr. Tapan, Dr. Deval, Dr. Ansul, Dr. Shoib for their help and co-operation.

I would also like to thank my juniors Dr.Sharan, Dr. Vijay, Dr.Sweth, Dr.Vaibhav, Dr.Prashant, Dr.Mohith, for their support and co-operation.

I am great full to my uncle Dr Ramesh Patil for his guidance,encouragements provided to me in my entire professional course.

I am deeply indebted to my parents for their blessings, which helped me to complete this dissertation.

Last but not the least; I convey my heartfelt gratitude to all my patients, without whose co-operation, this study would be incomplete.

DR. RAJENDRA GIRADDI

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

(In alphabetical order)

#	:	Fracture
&	:	And
ANT	:	Anterior
AP	:	Antero Posterior
AO	:	Arbeitsgemeinschaft Fur Osteosynthesefragen
ASIF	:	Association For The Study Of Internal Fixation
DEG	:	Degree
DHS	:	Dynamic Hip Screw
DIAM	:	Diameter
FIG	:	Figure
GTS	:	Greater Trochanter Splintering
IT	:	Intertrochanteric
LAT	:	Lateral
MED	:	Medial
OA	:	Osteoarthritis
OTA	:	Orthopaedic Trauma Association
PFN	:	Proximal Femoral Nail
POST	:	Posterior
TAD	:	Tip Apex Distance
TBPP	:	Trochanteric Buttress Plate
TFN	:	Trochanteric Femoral Nail

ABSTRACT

As age increases, fall becomes more often so as intertrochanteric fracture of femur. These intertrochanteric fractures leads to high rates of morbidity and mortality as they need prolonged immobilization, but recent advances in modalities of internal fixation have improved results⁴.Because of early mobilisation. The Trochanteric Femoral Nail(TFN) is found effective and suitable in Indian population as it is smaller in size. Here is an effort to study the results of Trochanteric Femoral Nail in the management of intertrochanteric fractures by analyzing the factors which influence the postoperative mobility.

Materials and methods : Study was done in 30 patients with intertrochanteric fractures treated with trochanteric femoral nail. Patients were followed up at 6 wks, 3months, and 6 months. The intraoperative blood loss, duration of surgery, intra operative complications, post operative complication, duration of hospital stay were studied. functional outcome was assessed based on Kyle's criteria.

Results: In our series of 30 cases there were 22 male and 8 female, maximum age of 90 yrs and minimum age of 20 yrs, most of the patients were between 60 to 70 yrs. Mean age of 58 yrs. 63.3% of cases were admitted due to Domestic fall and 36.7% due to road traffic accidents with common predominance of both sides. AO Type 31A2 fracture accounted for 40 % of cases. Mean duration of hospital stay is 14 days and mean time of full weight bearing is 6 wks. Good to excellent results are seen in 81% cases, Fair in 16%, 3% case with poor results according to kyle's criteria.

Conclusion: Trochanteric Femoral Nail can be considered the most judicious and rational method of treating intertrochanteric fractures , especially the unstable and reverse oblique type.

Key words : TFN, Intertrochanteric fractures, functional out come

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INTRODUCTION

As age increases, fall becomes more often so as intertrochanteric fracture of femur. The increased prevalence of osteoporosis increases intertrochanteric fractures(1). Trivial fall accounts for 90% of intertrochanteric fractures in elderly due to osteoporotic bone^{2,3}. But in young individuals high energy trauma such as motor vehicle accident or fall from height.³

These intertrochanteric fractures leads to high rates of morbidity and mortality as they need prolonged immobilization, but recent advances in modalities of internal fixation have improved results⁴.

The primary goal of treatment is early mobilization, which can be achieved by good reduction and internal fixation .

The dynamic hip screw has been considered the device of choice because it is time tested implant in fracture union. The drawback of sliding hip screw is loss of hip offset and shortening of the leg.

Now fourth generation of intramedullary nails like proximal femoral nails gained popularity.⁵

Proximal femur nail were not found to be very effective in Indian population as there is anthropometric variation of proximal femur which may lead to an increased difficulty in placement of femoral neck screws. The Trochanteric Femoral Nail(TFN) is found effective and suitable in Indian population as it is smaller in size than Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN).⁶

Here is an effort to study the results of Trochanteric Femoral Nail in the management of intertrochanteric fractures by analyzing the factors which influence the postoperative mobility.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To clinically evaluate the functional outcome and associated complications of intertrochanteric fracture treated with Trochanteric Femoral Nail.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORICAL REVIEW:

Sushruta the store house of Aryan surgery in 5th century A.D., divided fractures into 12 types and dislocations into 6 types. He has also described the clinical features of fractures. He treated fractures and dislocations with a special splint made of bamboo which was subsequently adopted by the British Army as the “patient rattan cane” splint.

Egyptians also practiced Orthopaedics and have recorded the use of crutches. An Egyptian demonstrated his wisdom in treating a case of spinal fracture and his treatment is not so different from some recent methods.

Greece then replaced Egypt as a centre of culture as well as medical development. The basis for the scientific study and practice of medicine arises from “Corpus Hippocraticum” the remarkable systematic treatise of medicine and surgery written elaborately lengthily by physician of Alexandrian school between 4th century B.C. and 1st century A.D. and ascribed to Hippocrates. This book is quite modern and includes use of traction manipulation and splints.

The great French surgeon “Ambrose Pare” first described the fracture at the upper end of femur in 1564.

Sir Astley Cooper (1768-1841), the outstanding English surgeon published his book on management of fractures and dislocations (1825). He classified the fractures at the upper end of femur into:

1. Intracapsular fractures
2. Extracapsular fractures
3. Fractures through greater trochanter.

This classification is still valid. He also recognized the difference in prognosis of intracapsular and extracapsular fractures of proximal femur.

In 1852 Antonius Mathijssen (1803-1875) introduced the plaster of Paris bandage. This was the most important development in the management of fractures.

Hugh Owen Thomas (1834-1891) who belongs to an English family of bone setters, became the foremost British Orthopaedician of the 19th century. He developed the Thomas splint (1876) which is useful even today. He was a firm advocate of the principle of continuous immobilization in the management of fractures.

In 1860 Buck introduced adhesive plaster traction in the treatment of fractures.

In 1895 Roentgen discovered X-rays, an event which has resulted in great advances in diagnosing and treatment of fractures.

In 1895 Kocher classified fractures of the proximal femur an improvement over Cooper's classification.

In 1902, **Whitman observed** restoration of near normal anatomy of hip in proximal femur fracture by traction, abduction, and internal rotation and stabilization with implants.⁷

The "Balkon frame" devised by the Dutch during the Balkon wars in 1903 proved of the great value in the treatment of fractures by suspension and traction.

In 1909 Steinmann introduced skeleton traction with the Steinmann pin and Kwire which form the part of conservative management in fractures of proximal femur treatment.

The internal fixation of fractures with metal plates and screws was reported by Sir Arbuthnot Lane of London in 1894 and by Albin Lambotte of Belgium.

The introduction of the Tri-flanged nail by Smith-Peterson (1931) for the management of fracture neck of femur has resulted in a great reduction of mortality and improvement in the percentage of union.

In the 1930s, lag screw type of devices are introduced by **Henry, Littman, Henderson**, and others instead of nails.^{8,9,10}

In 1937, Thornton Plate an side plate bolted to the Smith-Petersen nail was introduced by **Lawson Thornton**.¹¹

Until 1940's the treatment of trochanteric fractures was reduction of the fractures, and immobilization either in hip spica or in traction.

In 1941 Jewett introduced fixed angle nail plate for the management of Trochanteric fractures, which was a breakthrough to conservative treatment.

In 1945 Virgin and Mar Ausland introduced the screw, which produce a Dynamic compression at the fracture site.

In 1949 Boyd and Griffin first classified the types of Trochanteric fractures. In same year E. Mervyn Evans classified Trochanteric fractures as stable and unstable.

In 1949, Boyd and Griffin introduced Trochanteric buttress plate with Neufeld plate for unstable fractures to prevent medicalization.

In 1950, intertrochanteric fractures management were begins with external fixation, but it became failure due to increased rate of pin-tract infection, pin loosening, instability, and failure.^{12,13,14}

In 1955 Schumpelick W. Jantzen published the use of sliding screw plate and in the same year Pugh and Badgely in USA developed a sliding nail with a trifin tip to avoid the joint penetration.

In 1960 a USA based "Richards manufacturing company" produced dynamic compression screw and hence it is also known as Richards screw.

In 1985 Gamma nail was developed after cadaver studies and clinically on 421 patients.

In 1993 sliding plate (Medoff) was devised for DHS in the treatment of intertrochanteric fractures.

In 1996, AO/ASIF Developed a new device **Proximal Femoral Nail** which has been useful in early mobilization and treatment of unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures.¹⁵

In 2000, Gottfried developed the **Percutaneous Compression Plate (PCCP) system**, to provide rotational stability to the intertrochanteric fractures fixation, and it minimises the damage to the greater trochanter (lateral wall of the femur).¹⁶

The **Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation (PFNA) system** was developed by the AO/ASIF in 2004. The main design characteristic of the implant is the use of a single blade with a large surface area. Insertion of the blade compactsthe cancellous bone. These characteristics provide optimal anchoring and stability when the implant is inserted into osteoporotic bone.¹⁷

In **June 2004**, the **Short Proximal Femoral Nail** was introduced in India by **Gadegone WM and Salphale YS**.

In **April 2010**, **Gadegone WM, Salphale YS** concluded after reviewing outcomes of 100 Asian patients who underwent short proximal femoral nailing for stable and unstable intertrochanteric fractures. They concluded that **Trochanteric Nail** is a superior implant for stable and unstable intertrochanteric fractures in terms of operating time, surgical exposure, blood loss, and complications, especially for patients with relatively small femur.¹⁸

The PFN has a proximal diameter of 15 cm, expanded to give additional strength. The proximal 2 screws are of 6.4 mm and 8 mm. Both screws are self-tapping and partially threaded to allow for sliding compression. The distal screws are of 4.9 mm fully threaded self-tapping locking bolt. The nail has 6 degrees valgus bend proximally. It is available in short and long versions from 240 to 420 mm in length. It is available in 10 to 12 mm of distal diameter and neck shaft angle of 125 to 135 deg. The advantages of proximal femoral nail over the sliding hip screw¹⁹.

- a) A Proximal femoral nail provides more efficient load transfer.
- b) A Proximal femoral nail has shorter lever arm which decreases tensile strain on the implant so decreasing the risk of implant failure.
- c) Because a Proximal femoral nail incorporates a sliding hip screw, the advantage of controlled fracture impaction is maintained.
- d) Intramedullary location of the Proximal femoral nail limits the amount of sliding and therefore limb shortening and deformity that can occur.
- e) Proximal femoral nail requires shorter operative time and less soft tissue dissection than a sliding hip screw, so decreasing the overall morbidity.

G. S. Kulkarni et al²⁰ reviewed the current concepts of treatment of Intertrochanteric fractures. They concluded that unstable Intertrochanteric fractures can be helped by medullary fixation as there is more failure of Dynamic hip screw. Proximal femoral nail developed by A.O. has two sliding screws. Advantages of their screws are:

1. More stable fixation.
2. Prevention of rotational deformity.

Simmermacher R. K et al²¹ reviewed 191 patients having proximal femoral fractures treated with PFN in one year. After the 4 months of follow up technical failures were seen in just 4.6% of the cases. They concluded that the result of this new

implant compare favourably to the currently available implants for the treatment of the unstable pertrochanteric femoral fractures.

Christian Boldin, Franz J. Seibert et al²² in 2000 carried a prospective study 55 patients having proximal femoral fractures treated with the Proximal femoral nail. They achieved good results in most of the patients with very less complications at 12 month follow up. They concluded that Proximal femoral nail is a good minimal invasive implant for unstable proximal femoral fractures.

Pajarinen J. et al²³ performed a randomised clinical trial comparing the Dynamic hip screw and Proximal femoral nail in patients with pertrochanteric fractures emphasizing functional outcomes and rehabilitation. At four months review patients treated with proximal femoral nail regained their pre-injury walking ability, Shortening of the both femoral neck and shaft was seen in patients treated with Dynamic hip screw, this difference was statistically significant.

Klinger H. M. et al²⁴ have done a study on Dynamic hip screw and trochanteric buttress plate Vs proximal femoral nail in management of 173 unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures. In case of proximal femoral nail 17.2% revisions were necessary and in the case of dynamic hip screw with TBPP 21.6%. A shorter operation time and a considerable shorter in patient stay were common with proximal femoral nail. They concluded that Dynamic hip screw with TBPP had a higher incidence of complications in unstable trochanteric fractures than proximal femoral nail.

Reska M. et al²⁵ reviewed 83 patients with proximal femoral fractures treated with Proximal femoral nail. In their study except for 2 cases post-operative course was favourable in rest of the patients. They concluded that with the use of proximal femoral nail early mobilisation of patient is possible. A careful surgical approach and

technique with a stable Osteosynthesis have markedly contributed to a more rapid mobilization of a patient with the use of proximal femoral nail.

Pavelka T. et al²⁶ reviewed 79 patients with ipsilateral fractures of the hip and femoral shaft treated with a long proximal femoral nail. In follow up for at least 12months bone union was achieved in all patients.. The outcomes were excellent in 64%, good in 28% and satisfactory in 8%. They concluded that the long proximal femoral nail is a high quality implant that increases our options of treatment of all the reconstruction nails.

W.M. Gadegone and Y.S. Salphale²⁷ in 2006 carried out a study on 100 consecutive patients who had suffered an Intertrochanteric or high subtrochanteric fractures treated with Proximal femoral nail. Complications occurred in 12 patients. They concluded that Osteosynthesis with the Proximal femoral nail offers the advantage of high rotational stability of the head-neck fragment.

Ramesh Krishna.K²⁸ in 2009 carried out a study on 30 patients with Intertrochanteric fractures treated with Dynamic hip screw and Proximal femur nail with follow up of 6 months, 5 patients lost for follow up (3 dynamic hip screw and 2 proximal femur nail) and two patients expired due to associated medical problems. They conclude that proximal femur nail is better alternative to dynamic hip screw in the management Intertrochanteric fractures it reduces operating time , radiation exposure , blood loss and intra-operative complications but it is technically difficult and need more expertise.

In 2009, A retrospective study was conducted of 26 cases, they concluded that in the management of unstable intertrochanteric fractures PFN is a suitable implant which needs open reduction and internal fixation. It has less intra operative and postoperative morbidity.²⁹

EgolKA, ChangEY, CvitkovicJ, KummerFJ, KovalKJ (2004)³⁰ did a study on the mismatch of current intramedullary nails with the anterior bow of the femur. They inferred that at the implant which are developed according to western population were oversized, had the intra-operative complications such as splintering and fractures.

The available length of proximal femoral nail in India is of 240-250 mm. In an average Indian subject, it passes through the mid-diaphysis of the femora and occasionally abuts against the bowed femora. This may cause the intra-operative femoral shaft fractures and thigh pain, due to implant touching the anterior cortex of the femur.

The fixation of intramedullary nail is affected by the anterior curvature of the femur.

If there is significant difference in the nail and the anterior femoral curvature leads to cortical penetration or fracture angulation.³¹

The proximal diameter of the gamma nail and proximal femoral nail is 15mm, which is too large for average Indian femora, which may give rise to widening of the trochanter and fractures. In Chinese population a study has been done with the modification in the gamma nail by reducing its diameter and length.³²

In the series of 295 patients with trochanteric fractures treated with the PFN by Domingo et al. the average age of the patients was 80 years, which possibly accounted for 27% of the patients who developed complications in the immediate postoperative period.

TROCHANTERIC FEMORAL NAIL (TFN)

The TFN has the following modifications for the Indian population. It is having a smaller proximal diameter of 14mm. The proximal 2 screws are of 6.4mm and 8mm. The distal bolts are of 4.9mm bolts. The nail has 6 degrees valgus bend

proximally. It is available in length 180mm standard . Available in 10, 11 and 12mm of distal diameters and neck shaft angle of 130 and 135 deg.

The advantages of the TFN as an intramedullary device

- a) Due to its location in intramedullary fixation provides more efficient load transfer than does a sliding hip screw.
- b) It decreases the tensile strength due to its shorter lever arm, thus decreasing the risk of implant failure.
- c) Because an intramedullary fixation device incorporates a sliding hip screw, the advantage of controlled fracture impaction is maintained.
- d) It decreases the complications like limb shortening and deformity by limiting the amount sliding of fracture fragment .
- e) The Operative time to insert the intramedullary hip screw requires shorter time. It requires less soft tissue dissection than a sliding hip screw, so decreasing the overall morbidity.

In addition it has several other favourable characteristics

1. The presence of two proximal screws provides better rotational control of proximal fracture fragment.
2. It allows length and rotational control even when the lesser trochanter is not intact.
3. It can be dynamically locked.

The main advantages of TFN over its precursor gamma nail are. Since the 2 proximal screws are smaller in diameter, it is not necessary for the nail to be stout unlike gamma nail and hence theoretically induces less comminution of proximal segment and less disruption of abductor insertion.

Gadegone WM, Salphale YS (April 2010)³³ reviewed outcomes of 100 Asian patients who underwent Trochanteric Nailing for stable and unstable intertrochanteric fractures. They concluded, that short proximal femoral nail is a superior implant for stable and unstable intertrochanteric fractures in terms of operating time, surgical exposure, blood loss, and complications, especially for patients with relatively small femora.

TFN (Trochanteric Femoral Nail) is a newly introduced intra medullary device has advantages over PFN. Because of its short length and tapering distal end leads to less stress at the distal tip, this reduces risk of fracture at distal tip. Because of short length, TFN can be used in femur with increased bowing or altered anatomy of distal half of femur. Straighter configuration and availability of distal jig reduce operative time as compared to PFN.

A study was done by Mandal S, Kundu S, Hyam A, in Short-term evaluation of results of trochanteric femoral nailing (TFN) “in comminuted unstable trochanteric hip fractures” in 25 cases. In that study All cases show union, majority (64%) within 16wks. In 80% patients Harris hip score was >70 within 10 wks. In 60% cases shows excellent alignment. The complications like neck-screw cut out, and varus malunion is lesser than DHS. With respect to collapse of fracture area TFN gave more stable fixation than gamma nail. The stress-rising effect of PFN over the anterior femoral cortex can be avoided by using TFN.

In their Study they concluded that, unstable intertrochanteric fractures treated with TFN has more advantages than the extramedullary implants in terms of biological and biomechanical point of view. It is a minimally invasive intramedullary device and their clinical results were excellent as compared to techniques like gamma-nail and PFN, with less complications.³⁴

In Asian population further studies have to conduct to confirm the efficacy of the Trochanteric femoral nail.

SURGICAL ANATOMY^{35,36,37,38}

The hip joint is a **multiaxial synovial joint** of the **ball and socket variety**, formed by the femoral head & the acetabulum.

BONE STRUCTURE (Fig. 1 & 2)

The femoral head is an imperfect sphere of cancellous bone covered by articular cartilage. The size of the head varies in proportion to the body mass varying from 40 to 60 mm in diameter.

The femoral neck comprises the region from the head to the intertrochanteric region. The neck forms an angle of 125 to 140 degree with the shaft in the antero posterior plane & angle of 10-20 deg (anteversion) in the lateral plane. The intertrochanteric region consists of the greater & lesser trochanter, representing a zone of transition from the neck to the shaft. This area consists primarily of dense trabecular bone that serves to transmit & distribute stress. The *Calcar femorale*, is a vertical wall of dense bone extending from the posteromedial aspect of the femoral shaft to the posterior portion of the neck, which forms an internal trabecular strut within the inferior portion of the neck.

The subtrochanteric region, extends from the lesser trochanter to an area 5 cm distal to it. Subtrochanteric region had high stress concentration with large compressive forces medially & tensile forces laterally.

Fig 1 Ant view anatomy of proximal femur

Fig 2 Post view anatomy of proximal femur

Fig: 3 Trabecular pattern

Fig: 4 Regions of the proximal femur

Fig: 5 showing the Singh &Maini index with Gr.1 Representing severe osteoporosis &Gr.6 normal bone.

MUSCLES

There are numerous powerful muscles surrounding the trochanteric region.

The muscles can be grouped as follows:

THE ABDUCTORS

These muscles are the *gluteus medius* & *gluteus minimus* they originate from the outer table of the ilium & insert onto the greater tuberosity. The *tensor fascia lata* arises from the outer border of the iliac crest & inserts on the iliotibial band. The *glutei* control the pelvic tilt in the frontal plane.

Hip joint and Muscles around hip

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Fig 6

Fig 7

Hip joint and muscles around hip

Fig 8 muscles in lateral aspect

Fig 9 Muscles in Post aspect of hip

Fig 10 Hip joint and muscles around hip

THE FLEXORS

The *iliopsoas* inserts on the lesser trochanter. It is responsible for the displacement of this fragment in highly unstable fractures.

THE SHORT EXTERNAL ROTATORS

These muscles include the *piriformis*, *obturator internus*, *obturatorexternus*, *superior & inferior gemelli* & *quadratus femoris*. They insert along the posterior aspect along the intertrochanteric crest.

GLUTEUS MAXIMUS

This is the largest muscle of the body. It arises from the ilium, sacrum & coccyx & inserts into the iliotibial band & the gluteal tuberosity. It extends thigh, assists in its lateral rotation and assists in raising the trunk from flexed position.

BLOOD SUPPLY OF PROXIMAL FEMUR:

ARTERIAL BLOOD SUPPLY (Fig 11 & 12)

Extra capsular arteries to upper end of femur (entering the trochanters and base of neck) arise from,

1. Medial circumflex femoral artery. (which branch into)
 - a. Lateral epiphyseal artery
 - b. Superior metaphyseal artery
 - c. Inferior metaphyseal artery (supply head derived from metaphysis)
2. Lateral circumflex femoral artery
3. Superior gluteal artery
4. Obturator artery, Medial epiphyseal artery (artery of ligamentum teres branch from acetabular artery).
5. First perforating branch of profunda femoris artery.
6. Second and third perforating branch of profunda femoris artery (nutrient arteries). Arteries to the head and to major portion of neck are derived from both femoral circumflex arteries and to a variable degree from acetabular branch from Obturator artery. Acetabular branches pass through the acetabular notch to supply soft tissue in acetabular fossa, branches into the hip-bone and gives one or more branches (artery of ligamentum teres or foveolar artery) to the head through ligamentum teres. Its supply decreases to head from children to adult. Femoral circumflex arteries supply the intracapsular part of head and neck. Their branches have similar courses for they all pierce the fibrous capsule of the joint at the intertrochanteric line anteriorly and neck of femur posteriorly and run up towards the head on the surface of neck (capsular/Retinacular arteries), deep to the synovial membrane

in its retinaculæ that is reflected upward around the neck from the attachment of fibrous capsule to the rim of cartilage covering the head. Because of this course, they are liable to interruption in any intracapsular fractures. These capsular vessels are divided into :

- Ascending branch
- Metaphyseal branch
- Epiphyseal branch

Lateral epiphyseal arteries supply 2/3rd of femoral head in adult. In subcapital fractures, metaphyseal vessels are torn when head fragment is grossly displaced, which places the head at risk of viability.

Medial epiphyseal vessels alone is left to supply the head, if lateral epiphyseal and metaphyseal vessels are involved, and is usually unable to maintain the viability of head. Vessels to capsule of the hip joint are branches that supply upper end of femur.

Fig: 11. Vascular supply of the proximal femur

Fig 12. Vascular supply of Proximal femur

VENOUS OUTFLOW:

Capsular veins course inferomedially along trochanteric line, then towards obturator foramen where they drain into obturator vein. Circumflex group of veins is a diffuse plexus in the basal portion of neck and greater trochanter, and leave at the level of lesser trochanter, to enter the femoral vein. Smaller veins on the posterior aspect of neck and greater trochanter, course to plexuses in the region of ischial tuberosity and greater sciatic notch. Minimal venous drainage occurs through veins of lineae aspera.

BLOOD SUPPLY TO HIP JOINT

It is from the branches of the most of the vessels in its neighbourhood i.e. medial and lateral femoral circumflex arteries, obturator artery, superior and inferior gluteal arteries and perforating branch of profunda femoris artery.

NERVE SUPPLY TO HIP JOINT

It is innervated by articular branches from different nerves (mixed nerves)

1. **Primary:** direct branches from adjacent nerve trunks.

- Posterior articular nerve, branch of nerve to quadratus femoris, enters posterior capsule of the joint, and is the most important branch.
- Medial articular nerve, a branch from anterior division of obturator nerve through its lateral branch to pectineus and adductor muscles, and supply the anteromedial and inferior aspect of joint capsule.
- Nerve to ligamentum teres, a branch from posterior division of obturator nerve which supplies to obturator externus muscle.

2. **Accessory:** from nerves within muscles related to joint, supply a small portion of hip joint and arise mainly from femoral nerve through nerve to pectineus.

BIOMECHANICS OF THE HIP JOINT^{39,40}

The hip joint is a ball and socket joint. During weightbearing the forces are transmitted to the head and neck of femur at an angle of 165 degree to 170 degree regardless of the position of pelvis. High loading are sustained by the hip because of the powerful muscles across it. During loading the leverage of the femoral head and neck produces bending of the shaft. This bending forces generates compressive stress medially and tensile stress laterally. The compressive forces are higher than the tensile forces. This is called "Bending Movement". When the lever arm is longer, the bending movement is greater. The bending movement is one of the important factor of varus deformity, stressfractures of the implant and non-union.

Hip joint moves in all directions. In Saggital plane motion of flexion ranges from 0-140 degrees and 0-15 degree of extension. In frontal plane motion of adduction is 0-30 degrees and abduction 0-45 degrees. In transverse plane motion of internal rotation ranges from 0-30 degree and external rotation 0-40 degrees. The proximal fragment is abducted by abductors (Gluteus medius and minimus), is flexed by iliopsoas and externally rotated by the short external rotators. The adductors pull the distal fragment towards midline.

These muscle forces act upon the fixation device after operation even when patient is in the bed. In the hip joint the fulcrum is the centre of the hip and forces are body weight and abductor muscle tension. The distance from trochanter to the centre of the femoral head is shorter than the distance to the body's midline, so the abductors must exert more force than body weight to keep the pelvis balanced.

The variation in neck shaft angle will influence the relative ratio of the lever arm distance between the midline and the femoral head and the trochanter and will

there by influence the efficiency of the abductor muscles, even the hip is in valgus, the short abductor lever arm requires tremendous pull of the hip to balance the pelvis. In varus position the abductors do not have to work as hard to balance the pelvis. The force at the hip during single limb stance is around 2.5 times body weight. During dynamic activities that requires greater agonist and antagonist activity rises the stresses at the hip joint significantly.

It has been shown that in males an average hip joint reaction force is 4 times of bodyweight occurs immediately after heel strike with another peak of 7 times body weight at toe off. In females, the magnitudes of joint reaction forces are decreased, with first peak approximately 2.5 times body weight and second peak approximately 4 times body weight.

Rydell showed that standing on one leg generated a force 2.5 times body weight in that hip. At rest with two leg support, there was a force of about half the body weight across each hip joint where as standing the hip and knee flexed 90 degree increased the force to rear body weight across the flexed hip. Running increases the force to 5times body weight. Lifting the leg from supine position with the knee straight produces a force of 1.5 times body weight across the hip joint.

PATHOMECHANICS OF INJURY

CAUSATIVE MECHANISM OF INTERTROCHANTERIC FRACTURES

Intertrochanteric fractures occur as a result of fall, involving both direct and indirect forces.

The suggested two mechanisms of injury are³⁶:

1. A blow to the trochanter region due to fall
2. Lateral rotation of the limb with osteoporotic and weakened bone may also be a factor for early and frequent fractures. The severity of the fracture is directly related to the degree of osteoporosis, which results in a weakened bone stock.

A 3rd recently suggested mechanism is the cyclical loading which produces micro and macro fractures which is commonly seen in osteoporotic and diseased bones.

Mechanism of bone failure^{41,42}

A structure will fail if it suffers an overload situation. An overload situation will occur if the system is unable to absorb the energy that is applied to it. In the hip joint area, this overload situation can occur as a result of number of independent but often interrelated factors, the following being important.

1. Falling
2. Impairment of energy absorbing mechanics
3. Bone weakness.

Falling

The body possesses of considerable amount of potential energy in the standing position. In falling, the potential energy changes to kinetic energy, which upon impact

with the floor must be absorbed by the structures of the body if a fracture is not to occur. There is sufficient potential energy in the standing body which, if unabsorbed at falling could break any bone in the body. In an average sized woman, the amount of potential energy to be observed in a fall would be approximately 4000 kg/cm and the energy absorbing capacity of the upper end of the femur is only 60 kg/cm approximately. Thus, if a bony injury is not to occur, the energy absorbing mechanisms must operate.

Impairment of energy absorbing mechanisms

The principal dissipation of energy is performed by active muscle contraction. This dissipation requires time and in the event of high speed trauma, there is not a sufficient period for muscular contraction to absorb energy before overloading of the bone has occurred and leads to failure. In the elderly, the neuromuscular response may be slower, and thus the energy absorption may not be rapid enough to prevent a fracture. In the elderly, the normal protective muscle contraction in the event of a slip rather than a fall, may lead to an uninhibited muscle contraction around the hip and produce a force as great as 600 kg/cm to fracture the neck of the femur without implicating any other factor.

Bone weakness

In osteoporosis or osteomalacia, bone weakens to about 1/4 of the normal healthy young bone and has a lower energy absorbing capacity leading to failure. Falling, impairment of energy absorbing mechanisms and bone weakness, all may contribute to fractures of the trochanter. It is mostly due to failure of the bone to withstand sudden bending or twisting forces acting on it when the patient is about to fall from standing position, impairment of energy absorbing mechanisms particularly in the elderly and in bone weakness, and more so in females leading to the fractures of the trochanter.

According to **HORN AND WANG**⁴³ the failure of the stress-resistance mechanism to operate either because of muscle weakness or delayed reaction time, especially in osteoporotic bones, may be an etiologic factor in the causation of intertrochanteric fractures.

FRACTURE ANATOMY

The fracture pattern is influenced by the muscles, which are attached to the various parts of the trochanteric region. The forces acting on the fracture and the bone quality influence the fracture pattern. Hence it is imperative to understand the muscles forces acting on this region.

The upper fragment lies in external rotation if the level of the fracture is such that short external rotators remain attached to it.

Fractures proximal to the attachment of short external rotators show external rotation of the distal fragment but not of the proximal fragment & also due to gravity.

Forward angulation occurs in the sagittal plane due to unbalanced muscle action the fracture opens up posteriorly with its apex pointing anteriorly, visible on X-rays as a gap.

FRACTURE GEOMETRY AND INSTABILITY

The fracture stability is largely dependent on the geometry of the fracture. The most commonly encountered patterns of instability are:

- Lesser trochanter comminution
- Reverse oblique fracture
- Intertrochanteric fracture with sub-trochanteric extension.

A truly stable Intertrochanteric fracture is one that when reduced has cortical contact without a gap posteriorly & medially. This contact will prevent further

displacement into varus & retroversion. In the stable fracture the posterior & medial cortices are not comminuted & there is no displaced fracture of the lesser trochanter.

The importance of the lesser trochanter is the key to evaluating the stability of the fracture. The size & amount of displacement of this fragment are the critical factors in this evaluation. Up to 60% of Intertrochanteric fractures are unstable & hence at a risk of complications.

THE LATERAL WALL

The lateral wall of the trochanteric region has been given little importance in the past. Now it is believed that extensive comminution of the lateral wall requires to be repaired thus the development of the trochanteric plate to buttress the lateral wall⁴⁴.

REVERSE OBLIQUE FRACTURE

In this type of fracture the fracture line extends from lesser trochanter inferiorly to the lateral cortex. The geometry of the fracture is such that it is inherently unstable. If this fracture is missed & treated with a sliding hip screw with plate it results in medialization of the distal fragment & a day one failure. Such fractures are best treated with a 95 blade plate or an intramedullary nail^{45,46}.

INTERTROCHANTERIC FRACTURE

WITH SUB-

TROCHANTERIC EXTENSION :

These are highly unstable injuries. The marked comminution of the posteromedial buttress combined with distal extension of the fracture renders them unstable. The distal extension of this fracture often makes plating difficult & an intramedullary nail is the better option.

CLASSIFICATIONS

Numerous classifications have been described for intertrochanteric fractures. An ideal classification should be able to describe the fracture, give guidelines regarding the Treatment & also have prognostic value.

The numerous fracture classifications are:

- 1. EVANS CLASSIFICATION⁴⁷(1949)**
- 2. BOHLER'S CLASSIFICATION (1936)**
- 3. BOYD & GRIFFIN CLASSIFICATION⁴⁸(1949)**
- 4. KYLE & GUSTILO CLASSIFICATION⁴⁹(1979)**
- 5. TRONZO CLASSIFICATION(1973)⁵⁰**
- 6. J.C.SCOTT'S CLASSIFICATION⁵¹**
- 7. MURRAY AND FREW (1949)⁵²**
- 8. JENSEN & MICHAELSON CLASSIFICATION⁵³(1975)**
- 9. HAFNER'S CLASSIFICATION⁵⁴**
- 10. W.K. MASSIE'S CLASSIFICATION⁵⁵(1963)**
- 11. A.O. & O.T.A. (MULLER) CLASSIFICATION^{36,56}(1990)**
- 1. EVAN'S CLASSIFICATION (Fig. 13)**

Evans in 1949, made an important step in understanding the stability of the intertrochanteric fractures. He observed that the key to a stable reduction is the restoration of the posteromedial cortical continuity. In the stable group the posteromedial cortex is intact or is minimally comminuted, making it possible to obtain a stable reduction. Unstable fractures on the other hand have extensive posteromedial comminution & displacement they are inherently unstable. Stability can be restored by obtaining opposition of the posteromedial cortex. The reverse oblique

fracture is inherently unstable because of the tendency of the shaft to displace medially.

Fig. 13. Evan's Classification

2. BOHLER'S CLASSIFICATION: (1936)

TYPE I:

Fracture through the base of the neck of femur with minimal displacement.

TYPE II:

Fracture through the trochanter and wide gap occurs between the two fragments of bone, an angle opening upwards.

TYPE III:

This is the commonest variety where the base of the neck is deeply driven into the spongy

mass of the trochanters. The lesser trochanter is frequently broken off.

TYPE IV:

Fracture through the trochanter with comminution. Here the neck is impacted but the shaft of the femur is displaced upwards parallel to the main fragment. Bohler recommends that TYPE I and II fractures should be treated by continuous traction and plaster spica for atleast ten weeks. In TYPE III the limb should be kept in extreme abduction and moderate internal rotation and maintained for atleast 14 weeks. In type IV traction is applied along the long axis of the body because abduction produces coxavalga.

3. BOYD AND GRIFFIN'S CLASSIFICATION: (1949)

Their classification included all fractures from the extra capsular part of the neck to a point 5cms distal to the lesser trochanter

TYPE I:

Fractures extending along the Intertrochanteric line, from greater trochanter to the lesser trochanter.

TYPE II:

Comminuted fractures, the main fracture being along the inter trochanteric line, but with multiple fractures in the cortex.

TYPE III:

Fractures that are basically subtrochanteric, with atleast one fracture line passing across the proximal end of the shaft from just distal to the lesser trochanter, with varying degrees of comminution.

TYPE IV:

Fractures of the trochanteric region and the proximal shaft with fracture in at least two planes.

Reduction of TYPE I fractures are simple & can be maintained with little difficulty TYPE II, III & IV fractures are increasingly more difficult to reduce & to maintain reduction & are associated with more complications.

Fig. 14. Boyd and Griffin Classification

4. KYLE, GUSTILO & PRIMER'S CLASSIFICATION:

TYPE I:

Stable, undisplaced intertrochanteric fractures

TYPE II

Stable, displaced fractures with fracture of the lesser trochanter & a varus deformity.

TYPE III:

Intertrochanteric fracture, in which the lesser trochanter fragment is large. The posterior wall is exploded with the break of the inferior neck already displaced into

the medullary cavity of the shaft of femur. A variant of this type has in addition the greater trochanter fractured off and separated.

TYPE IV:

Comminuted unstable fracture with disengagement of the two main fragments, these are unstable with the posterior wall exploded, but the spike of the neck fragment is displaced outside or medial to the shaft.

TYPE V:

Trochanteric fractures with reverse obliquity of the fracture line. These are uncommon.

Tronzo recommends fixation for TYPE I & II fractures. In TYPE III since the medial spike is impacted, not medial displacement is required. TYPE IV fractures require medial displacement of the distal fragment and then fixation. TYPE V fractures are stabilized by notching the shaft fragment and jamming it in the neck for stability.

5. TRONZO'S CLASSIFICATION (1973):

Tronzo in 1973 has classified intertrochanteric fractures based on mode of reduction potential into five types. This classification is also widely used.

Type I

Incomplete trochanteric fractures with only greater trochanter fractured.

Type II

Uncomminuted bitrochanteric fractures with or without displacement with an intact posterior wall and a relatively small lesser trochanteric fragment.

Type III

Comminuted fractures in which the posterior wall is exploded with the beak of inferior neck already displaced into the medullary cavity of the shaft fragment. The lesser trochanteric fragment is large. These are unstable fractures.

Type IV

Comminutedtrochanteric fractures with disengagement of two main fragments.

Type V

Trochanteric fractures with reverse obliquity to the fracture line.

6. J.C.SCOTTTYPE I:

Consists of, oblique basal fractures, involving one or both trochanters with little or nodisplacement.

TYPE II:

Consists of, oblique basal fractures, with varying degrees of comminution&displacement.

TYPE III:

Consists of, fractures with reversed obliquity, involving the lesser trochanter &less frequently with separation of the greater trochanter. The first two types of fractures do well with any method of treatment. The third group provided most of the problems &whatever method of treatment is employed, the results were uniformly discouraging. The third group of fractures was less troublesome than the second.

7. MURRAY AND FREW (1949):

Based onthe presence of the medial comminution.

TYPE I:

Stable, that is no medial comminution.

TYPE II:

Unstable, that is displaced lesser trochanter or larger femoral-arch fragment. This classification emphasizes the importance of the calcar femorale and the medial cortical buttress. This classification does not take into account the posterolateral instability caused by the difficulty in obtaining sufficient reduction of fractures in the lateral plane.

8. Modified EVAN'S by JENSEN AND MICHAELSON (1975):

Type I

Undisplaced, two fragment fractures

Type II

Displaced, two fragment fractures

Type III

Three fragment fractures without posterolateral support due to displaced greater trochanter

TYPE IV

Three fragment fractures without medial support due to displaced lesser trochanter or femoral arch fragments

TYPE V

Four fragment fractures without medial or postero-lateral support. The classification of EVAN'S is rather simple & based on the presence of mechanical instability as related to detachments of the lesser & greater trochanters. This classification has been used in numerous publications. The Evan's classification has been slightly modified based on their assessment of stability of the fracture on the primary radiographs after the injury and after reduction during surgery.

9. BASED ON PRIMARY DISPLACEMENT: (HAFNER, 1951) :

TYPE I: Undisplaced

TYPE II: Displaced

The simplest possible method of classifying trochanteric fractures is to divide them into displaced & undisplaced. This leads to fairly reliable information about the reduction but does not give sufficient grading.

10. W.K. MASSIE'S CLASSIFICATION (1963):

TYPE I: Stable, undisplaced

TYPE II: Stable, displaced

TYPE III: Unstable, displaced.

11. A.O. (MÜLLER) CLASSIFICATION:

The classification system devised by Müller & the A.O. group is extremely comprehensive & complete. Each region of the skeleton is assigned an alpha- numerical.

Value & is further classified into a type & a sub group. Schatzker⁵¹ has noted an inter- & intra- observer concordance of close to 100% for fracture type, 80-85 % for fracture group, 50-60 % for fracture sub-type. The inter trochanteric fractures have been assigned the number -**31 A**

They are further classified as:

- 31-A1- Proximal trochanteric
- 31-A2- Pertrochanteric multifragmentary
- 31-A3- Intertrochanteric

Each group is then further classified into three subgroups:

- 31-A-1

31-A1.1-Along intertrochanteric line

31-A1.2-Through greater trochanter

31-A1.3-Below lesser trochanter

- 31-A2

31-A2.1-With one intermediate fragment

31-A2.2-With several intermediate fragments

31-A2.3-Extending more than 1cm below lesser trochanter

- 31-A3

31-A3.1 Simple oblique

31-A3.2 Simple transverse

31-A3.3 Multifragmentary

Fig 15 .AO Classification of Intertrochanteric fractures

MANAGEMENT

CLINICAL FEATURES:

A history of trivial trauma, usually a slip in the bathroom or while walking, inability to stand up after the fall and pain around the hip joint in an elderly is the usual presentation.

CLINICAL FEATURES:

1. The limb is usually markedly shortened with external rotation deformity. The external rotation is usually greater than that seen in patients with intracapsular fractures of the neck of femur, lateral border of the foot touching the bed.
2. There may be swelling in the hip region, and ecchymosis over the greater trochanter may be seen later.
3. Tenderness over greater trochanter
4. Broadening and irregularity of greater trochanter
5. Supratrochanteric shortening

INVESTIGATION

1. Standard radiographic examination
 - a. Antero posterior view of the pelvis with both hip joints
 - b. Cross table lateral view of the involved proximal femur

Anteroposterior view is useful to know the fracture pattern and extent, quality of the bone, and allows comparison with the contralateral side to identify undisplaced and impacted fracture.

AP view in 10-15 deg of internal rotation will give the true view of

the proximal femur. In severe comminuted fractures, x-rays taken with traction help in understanding the fracture geometry better.

An AP view of the contralateral side helps in measurement of neck shaft angle and for preoperative planning.

The lateral view helps to assess size, location and comminution of posterior fragment and helps to determine the fracture stability.

2) M.R.I. and bone scans are useful in the diagnosis of occult fractures.

TREATMENT

Intertrochanteric fractures can be treated both by conservative & operative methods.

TYPES OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENTS

The various conservative methods used in a patient who is unfit for surgery or unwilling for surgery are⁵⁷:

1. De-rotation boot.
2. Buck's extension skin traction.
3. Skeletal traction.
4. Hamilton Russell traction.
5. Modified Russell's traction.
6. Fisk's and Perkin's method.

1) De-rotation boot: A below knee plaster cast is applied from tibial tuberosity up to the base of the toes with a wooden bar attached to the heel to prevent lateral rotation. After clinical and radiological union of fracture (10-12 wks), it is removed and physiotherapy is begun. This is an old form of treatment.

2) Buck's extension skin traction: adhesive plaster is applied to skin below knee of the affected limb with a spreader bar and light weight.

3) Skeletal traction: this is the commonest method used in conservatively treated cases. Heavy skeletal traction is used through the upper tibial skeletal pin over a BÖHLER BROWN splint. About 10% of the body weight is used for the traction; patient is advised to do the quadriceps exercise for the five minutes every one hourly. After 10-12 weeks traction is removed and patient is gradually mobilized and walking aids are used initially till consolidation of the fracture.

4) Hamilton Russell traction: Continuous traction is obtained in the line of the femur by the traction weight suspended through several pulleys. Since no splint is used the patient is more comfortable. The knee is flexed over a pillow and the limb is also supported while on traction, it is claimed that this controls both angulatory and rotational deformity.

5) Modified Russell's traction: Modification made here is the usage of a below knee plaster cast with one pulley incorporated.

6) Fisk's and Perkin's method: Continuous traction method over a complicated system of pulleys. There are many disadvantages of the conservative method of treatment. They are mainly knee joint stiffness, pin tract infections, deep vein thrombosis, pneumonia, prolonged hospital stay, bed sores etc. Coxavara deformity, shortening, limitation of the hip movements are the complications encountered around the hip. Mortality & the morbidity rates are very high in conservative line of treatment.

TYPES OF OPERATIVE METHODS^{58, 59}:

Intertrochanteric fracture, an injury of the elderly has a high mortality rate. Rapid patient mobilization following surgical stabilization of the fracture lessens the frequency of life threatening complications such as cardio-pulmonary failure

&thrombo-embolic diseases. It also minimizes the incidence of decubitus ulcers and limb contractures. Most intertrochanteric fractures are four part injuries, with secondary comminution of greater and lesser trochanters. The presence of the large posteromedial fragment defines an unstable pattern. Restoration of the bone opposition and stability by closed reduction on a fracture table is not possible in such cases with medial comminution. Successful reduction restores the osseous stability by achieving medial cortical abutment and impaction of the major fracture fragments in a normal or slight valgus alignment. An ideal fixation device should permit controlled intraoperative compression of the fracture and should allow the fracture to settle in a stable position and prevent nail protrusion through the femoral head. The device should act as an internal splint. Complications arise when the surgical construct is inadequate to withstand the major forces to which the proximal femur is subjected.

Some of these complications are:

- Varus settling of the fracture.
- Cutting out or protrusion of the nail or screw.
- Fatigue failure of the implant.

Relative contraindications to the surgery are :

- Contaminated wound at the operative site.
- Septicemia
- Delay in the treatment more than 3 wks
- Other associated conditions e.g. cardiopulmonary diseases, thromboembolic diseases etc.

Reconstitution of the medial buttress of unstable fractures by inter fragmentary compression screws decreases the likelihood of limb shortening and abductor insufficiency. Most patients under 65 years of age and active patients over 65 years of

age benefit from this additional surgery. Severe medial comminution or advanced osteoporosis may preclude successful inter fragmentary fixation. Cancellous bone grafting of medial cortical defects is occasionally necessary in young patients with unstable fractures. Elderly osteoporotic patients may be managed by one of the two techniques.

The major head/neck and shaft fragment may be aligned on the fracture table, so that femoral length is restored without concern for the trochanteric fractures. A sliding nail or screw plate implant allows post operative settling and stabilization of the fractures as necessary.

Intra operative medial bony contact and stability can be obtained by medial displacement of the femoral shaft or valgus osteotomy.

Although these procedures do obviate the need for anatomically nailed fractures to migrate in to stable position, they do shorten limb and abductor mechanism. A variety of internal fixation devices are available. They are mainly two types:

Extra medullary devices:

- Fixed angle nail plates
- Smith Peterson's nail and plate
- Jewett nail and plate
- Thompson nail and plate
- Holt nail and plate
- McKee nail and plate
- Liverpool nail and plate
- Northampton nail and plate
- McLaughlin nail and plate

- Neufeld nail and plate
- Sarmiento nail and plate
- A. O. blade plate
- Compression screws nail plates
- Richard's
- Zimmer
- Calandruccio
- Depuy
- Medoff plate
- Dynamic hip screw
- Deyerle assembly
- Massie and Pugh nail plates

Intramedullary devices:

- Cephalomedullary
- Ender's nail
- Kuntschercondylocephalic Y nail
- Harris condylocephalic nail
- Russell-Taylor interlocking nail
- Zickle nail
- Gamma nail
- Intramedullary hip screw
- Proximal femoral nail (AO)
- Trochanteric femoral nail
- Proximal femoral nail asia (AO)
- Short recon nail

- External fixation devices

Prosthetic replacement :

- Thompson's prosthesis
- Bipolar prosthesis
- Total hip replacement

NAIL PLATE DEVICES:

The fixed angle nail plate device was first developed by Thorton later modified by Holt, Jewett, Sarmiento, McLaughin etc. These devices were widely used in the past before invention of sliding screw plate devices. This nail does not allow control collapse. But with this, penetration of the nail in to the femoral head and in to the joint occurred with the collapse of the fracture. So a stable reduction before nail insertion is essential to prevent this complication. But this gives a poor grip in the proximal fragment increasing the chances of reangulation and migration of the nail within the femoral head. Later modification was "Holt nail", in which the plate is fixed to the femur by bolts rather than screws. It is much stronger than Jewett nail plate device.

SLIDING NAIL PLATE DEVICES:

In 1950's this device was introduced by Schumpelick and Jantzen, Pugh and Massie. These nails are very widely used and more technically demanding. It is available in 120 -150° barrel plate.

PRINCIPLE:

To allow control impaction (collapse) were the shearing force on the femoral head is transferred to the axis of the sliding screw to produce a compression force (act as a lag screw) when fragments collapse the stem will back out within the barrel of

the device. Clawson pointed out that to ensure impaction the barrel of the hip screw should not cross the fracture site. The screw has either sharp end or blunt end, the latter prevents the head penetration. Dynamic hip screw has been shown to be superior to nail plate. Screw threads of the nail enhance the purchase in the osteoporotic bone and the groove in the barrel plate prevents rotation. Jamming, bending or failure to slide the screw acts as fixed angle nail plate.

Advantages of the Dynamic hip screw:

- Decreases the penetration of the nail into the acetabulum.
- Improves postoperative mobility.
- Less residual pain.
- Decreases the reoperative rate.
- Decreases the incidence of the breakage.
- Decreases the incidence of the non-union.

Failures of the dynamic hip screw:

- Cutting out of the screw from the femoral head.
- Pulling of the slide plate from the femoral shaft.
- Disengagement of sliding compression hip screw from the barrel.
- Breakage of the hip screw.
- More bigger incision and trauma to the abductor mechanism.
- More blood loss.
- Fracture hematoma is lost as the site is opened.
- Need of an osteotomy in an unstable fractures.
- Delay weight bearing.

INTRA MEDULLARY DEVICES:

The intramedullary nails have gained popularity after 1970's. Ender first reported in 1970's the use of multiple flexible condyle cephalic nail that were introduced through the distal femur without opening the fracture site. These are indicated in the peritrochanteric fractures in elderly patients. After which several intramedullary devices has been introduced. They have several advantages over the traditional Dynamic hip screw. They are:

- Decreases the operative time and mortality.
- Decreases blood loss.
- Minimal surgical trauma.
- Decreases the radiation exposure.
- Medialization of the implant so more effective lever causing less stress on the implant.
- Decreasing the hospital stay of the patient.
- Effectively used in the unstable fractures so no need for bone loosening osteotomies.

There are several disadvantages with intramedullary devices. Here are some

- They are costly compare to D.H.S.
- Technically demanding procedure and requires good quality instruments as well as good image control by C-arm.
- Due to its proximal portion greater trochanter can splinter while inserting the nail. Hence the newer trochanteric femoral nails having smaller 14mm diameter of the tip proximally. It prevents the splintering of greater trochanter. Periprosthetic fractures though less due to its narrow tip compare to other intramedullary devices can still occur.

- “Z” effect- in this the cervical screw penetrates into the joint while the hip screw backs out. It can be prevented by delayed weight bearing in the unstable or osteoporotic bones, and by putting the correct size of both the screws (usually the cervical screw is 10mm shorter than the hip screw). Reverse “Z” effect if when opposite occurs. Both can be also prevented intra-operatively by putting a wire around both the screws, this is done mainly in unstable fractures or lateral cortex comminution.

BIOMECHANICS OF THE INTERNAL FIXATION

The understanding of the biomechanical properties of implants used in intertrochanteric fractures is vital in knowing how implant failure & nonunion occur, especially in the unstable variety of intertrochanteric fractures. Several biomechanical & clinical studies have been done to study the way in which these implants behave in the body^{60,61,62}.

IMPLANT DESIGN

Main implants used in the treatment of intertrochanteric fractures are:

1. Dynamic hip screw (extramedullary devices)
2. Proximal Femoral Nail (intramedullary devices)

The dimensions of the Dynamic hip screw are :

Plate	:	Thickness	–	5.8 mm
		Width	–	10 mm
		Holespacing	–	16 mm
		Barrel diam.	–	12.5 mm
		Barrel angle	–	130,135,140, 145 & 150.
		Barrel length	–	long 32 mm ,Short 25 mm.
• Screw	:	Shaft diam.	–	8mm

- Thread diam. – 12mm
- Thread length – 16mm & 32 mm
- Screw length – 60 to 130 mm (in 5mm increments)

The dimensions of the Proximal Femoral Nail (P.F.N) are:

- Diameter : Proximal – 15 mm
Distal – 10, 11 & 12 mm
- Valgus bend : 6 degrees
- Length : 240 mm to 420mm
- Screw diam. : Proximal – 6.4 mm (hip pin) & 8mm(neck screw)
Distal – 4.9 mm
- Screw angle : 125,130 & 135 degrees.

The dimensions of the Trochanteric Femoral Nail (T.F.N) are:

- Diameter : Proximal – 14mm
Distal – 10, 11 & 12 mm
- Valgus bend : 6 degrees
- Length : 180mm
- Screw diameter : Proximal – 6.4 mm (hip pin) & 8mm(neck screw)
Distal – 4.9mm
- Screw angle : 125,130 & 135 degrees.

BIOMECHANICAL ADVANTAGE OF THE INTRA MEDULLARY DEVICE

Lindsey⁶³, in his study has pointed out the numerous advantages of the intramedullary device with sliding screw:

1. To provide fixation of the head & neck.
2. To allow femoral head & neck collapse & subsequent impaction of the fracture site.
3. To lie within the intra medullary canal thus reducing the lever arm.
4. The implant itself serves as a buttress against lateral translation of the proximal fragment
5. To provide bone graft from the reamed products

SLIDING PROPERTIES

The sliding properties of both implants vary considerably. Sliding is an essential principle in the management of intertrochanteric fractures. Sliding permits impaction of the fracture fragments thus promoting healing.

Kyle⁶⁴ in his extensive study of the biomechanical principles of the sliding hip screw has identified key factors that promote sliding. A reduction in the bending forces is vital since bending forces reduce slide & cause jamming of the implant. The bending forces are increased by:

1. Longer extension of the screw.
2. Smaller screw angle.
3. Heavier patients.

In his subsequent studies on the sliding in second generation locked nails, Kyle⁶⁴ observed that sliding hip screw with plate needs less forces to initiate sliding as compared to initiate sliding in intra medullary devices. Amongst all intra medullary devices the Gamma nail requires the largest force. The explanation lies in

the barrel of the side plate, the barrel provides a free passage for the screw to slide, thus the longer the barrel length the less the forces required to initiate sliding.

BARREL PLATE ANGLE

The most routinely used barrel plate angle in most studies is 135 degrees; this is because of the ease of insertion & the more anatomical restoration of femoral neck angle.

However the 150 degree side plate has several advantages, since the forces are acting. More inline with the screw less bending forces act across the screw so relatively less.

Force is required to initiate sliding resulting in more impaction^{60,62}. Valgus hips are However more prone to develop early O. A.

SLIDING LENGTH

Gundle⁶⁵ has noted a positive correlation between sliding length & union. In his study he found that fractures fixed with a sliding length (i.e. the distance from proximal tip of the barrel to the distal thread of the screw) of less than 10 mm had 3 times higher rate of failure than those with sliding length more than 10 mm. This is particularly true in devices that have a 32mm threaded screw length with a 32 mm barrel. He thus recommends a short barrel for screws with less than 85 mm screw length.

FAILURE OF THE SLIDING HIP SCREW

Spivak⁶⁶ has noted 4 models of failure of the sliding hip screw:

1. Cutting out of the screw head (most common).
2. Jamming of the screw in the barrel.
3. Disengagement of the screw from the barrel.
4. Pulling out of the screw.

Cut out of the screw from the head is by far the most common mechanism of failure of the sliding hip screw. Screw cut out occurs as a result of:

1. Improper position.
2. Failure to achieve T.A.D.
3. Poor bone quality.

The above two factors are in the hands of the surgeon & can easily be prevented.

SCREW POSITION

The ideal position of the screw in the head is a debatable issue⁶¹. Most authors recommend a central placement in the head in both views while some accept a posterior & inferior placement. However all authors strongly condemn an anterior & superior placement.

TIP APEX DISTANCE

Baumgaertner⁶⁷ described the T.A.D as the distance from the tip of the screw to the subchondral bone in both the A.P. & lateral views .In his series of 120 cases he noted that not a single case screw cut out occurred if the T.A.D was maintained less than 25mmas compared to a historical control rate of 8 %.

Fig: 17 Tip Apex Distance

JAMMING OF THE SCREW

Kyle in his study⁶⁴ noted that jamming of the screw within the barrel will occur if the bending forces exceed the compressive forces & the screw will impact against the barrel. This situation is avoided by:

1. Maximum engagement of the screw in the barrel.
2. Use of valgus angle devices.

Jamming results in failure of the implant to slide & the device behaving as a fixed angle device.

STRAIN PATTERN

Rosenblum⁶⁰ in his biomechanical study of 10 cadaveric femoral noted that the Gamma nail had an increasing stiffness. This stiffness was a result of :

- The large proximal diameter (17 mm) of the proximal end
 - Larger compression screw diameter 12 mm as compared to 8 mm in the sliding hip screw.
 - The maximum deflection at the tip of the nail is inversely proportional to its movement of insertion & directly proportional to its length.
 - Thus the Gamma nail was stiffer than the sliding hip screw, making it more resilient to bending forces preventing compression at the fracture site.
 - The increased stiffness of the implant would transmit more force to the tip of the nail making the nail behave similar to a femoral prosthesis. This is the probable reason for the high incidence of fractures of the femoral shaft.
- Rosenblum, also noted an inversion in the stress pattern, with more load being borne at the tip of the nail than the medial femoral cortex, He observed that in the stable intertrochanteric fractures the unlocked & the locked nails had similar strain patterns.

TFN was designed with this in mind making it less stiff because it has:

1. Proximal diameter of 14mm.
2. Entry point is through GT and not piriformis fossa (more valgus).
3. Smaller diameter tip causing less stress concentration and less chance of fracture.
4. Hip screw and Antirotation screw provide good compression at fracture site with adequate bone stock for revision.

In addition it has several other favourable characteristics

1. The presence of two proximal screws provides better rotational control of proximal fracture fragment.
2. It allows length and rotational control even when the lesser trochanter is not intact
3. It can be dynamically locked.

The main advantages of TFN over its precursor gamma nail are Since the 2 proximal screws are smaller in diameter, it is not necessary for the nail to be stout unlike gamma nail and hence theoretically induces less comminution of proximal segment and less disruption of abductor insertion.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material for the present study was obtained from the patients admitted in _____

Department of Orthopaedics with diagnosis of Intertrochanteric fracture from Oct 2015 to march 2017.

A minimum of 30 cases were taken and the patients were informed about the study in all respects and informed consent was obtained from each patient.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

- By interview
- By follow up at intervals of 6wks, 3months, and 6months
- By clinical examination
- By analyzing case papers

Following inclusion and exclusion criteria were used.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patient who has been diagnosed as having intertrochanteric fractures.
2. Patients more than 18 years of age.
3. Patient who are fit for surgical intervention.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patient below 18 years of age.
2. Patients with subtrochanteric extension.
3. Patients with compound fractures.
4. Patients with pathological fractures.
5. Patients unfit for surgery.

Patients admitted with Intertrochanteric fracture were examined and investigated with X-ray pelvis with both hips AP and Lateral view (whenever possible). Skin traction was applied to all cases. Blood and urine examinations were ordered as follows:

INVESTIGATIONS

- Blood – Hb%, Total count, Differential count, E.S.R.
- Urine – Albumin, Sugar, microscopy.
- Blood grouping and Rh type
- Bleeding time and Clotting time.
- HIV, HbsAg.
- Blood urea.
- Blood sugar Level.
- ECG.

SPECIAL INVESTIGATIONS (In patients with age more than 40 years and as advised by an anesthetist)

- 2 D Echocardiography.
- Chest X –ray.

Physician opinions were taken as to the fitness of patient before surgery as & when necessary. X-ray were reviewed again and classified with using Orthopaedic Trauma Association (OTA) classification. All fractures were treated using a Trochanteric femoral nail. All patients were assessed by using the Kyle's criteria at the follow-ups. Proforma specially made for the study was used. Data collected at the end of the study was statistically compared and analyzed with the similar studies done before.

PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION

- The patients were taken up for surgery after obtaining written and informed risk consent of the nature and complications of the surgery. The operative site (lateral aspect of the thigh) was shaved and prepared with betadine scrub, a day prior to the surgery.
- Xylocaine test dose & tetanus toxoid injections were given preoperatively.
- All patients were started on antibiotics prophylactically. A third generation Cephalosporin was administered via IV route prior to induction of anaesthesia, and continued at 12 hourly intervals for 3-5 days, and switched over to oral form till the 12th day post-operatively, i.e. until suture removal.

PREOPERATIVE PLANNING

- 1. Assessment of neck shaft angle:** Neck shaft angle was measured on the unaffected side on an AP x-ray using a goniometer.
- 2. Assessment of nail diameter:** Nail diameter was determined by measuring diameter of the proximal femur on an AP x-ray.
- 3. Determination of proximal screw sizes:**
Approximate sizes of the compression and anti-rotation screws were measured in the head neck region. A 15mm smaller screw than compression screw was chosen for the anti-rotation screw to prevent Z-Effect.
- 4. Length of the nail:** A Short TFN nail 180mm was used in all our cases.

IMPLANT DETAILS

A short trochanteric femoral nail (Fig.30) has a length of 180 mm and proximal diameter of 14mm. The narrow proximal diameter enables easy insertion and reduces the risk of femoral fracture. Distally, it is available in 10, 11 and 12mm diameters.

The nail has a 6° medio-lateral

angle for easy insertion and a flexible distal tip to avoid stress generation and refracture. This nail is available in femoral neck angles of 130° and 135°. It has a

8mm compression screw and a 6.4mm antirotation/stabilizing screw proximal to it. Distally,

It has 4.9mm both static and dynamic locking bolts. The nail has a longitudinal slot throughout, so as to accelerate regeneration of the endosteal bone. The nail is made up of 316L stainless steel.

Fig18: INSTRUMENTS AND IMPLANT SET

SURGICAL STEPS

Patient were given spinal or epidural anesthesia and shifted to a radiolucent fracture table in a supine position. Operative leg was put on traction. Opposite limb was put in a full abduction as to give space for the C-arm in between the legs. Reduction was achieved by traction and internal rotation primarily and adduction or abduction as required. Reduction was checked in a C-arm with anterior-posterior and lateral view. Limb was scrubbed, then painted and draped under sterile condition. A 5cm incision was taken above the tip of the greater trochanter and deepened to the gluteus medius muscle. Tip of the greater trochanter palpated and minimal muscle attachment was cleared off. After this TFN was fixed in a following manner:

Fig no 19 Patient positioning

1. Entry point

Insertion of the guide pin: It should be just medial to tip of the greater trochanter at the virtual meeting point of the line drawn in the center of the neck and a line drawn in the femoral shaft 6° lateral.

Fig no 20 entry point and confirmation by C-Arm

2. Guide wire insertion

Guide wire: 2.8mm guide wire is inserted in to the femoral shaft and across the fracture site in 6° of valgus. Its position is checked in the C-arm and the entry is widened with the awl.

Fig no 21 Guide wire insertion

3. Reaming of the proximal femur

Reaming: Reaming of the proximal femur is done with the reamer provided with the set.

Reaming

4. Nail insertion

Nail insertion: Nail is fixed on the jig and the alignment is checked. Then the nail is inserted into the femur. The position of the holes for the hip screws is checked in the C-arm for the depth of the nail.

Fig no 22 Nail insertion with Zig attached

5. Placing the guide wire pins

Guide wire for the screws: Guide wires for the screws are inserted via the jig and the drill sleeve. The ideal position of the guide wires is parallel and in the lower half of the neck in AP views, in a single line in the center of the neck in the lateral views. The proximal wire is 10mm from the sub-chondral bone and the distal wire 5mm from the sub-chondral bone.

Fig no 23 Placing guide wire pins and confirmation under C-Arm

6. Inserting the screws after the final setting

Insertion of the screw: First the 8mm hip screw is inserted after reaming over the distal wire and then the 6.4mm cervical screw. The hip screw should be 5mm away from the sub-chondral bone and the cervical screw 10mm away from the sub-chondral bone or both the screw tip should make one horizontal line when joined.

Fig no 24 Insertion of Proximal screws and confirmation under C-Arm

Distal screws: one or two static or dynamic 4.9mm interlocking bolts are inserted via the jig in to the distal part of the nail. Out of which one is a static and another is a dynamic hole. It should be done after removing the traction along with the tightening of the proximal screws.

Fig no 25 Distal screw insertion

The final position of the nail was checked in the C-arm in both views and the wound was closed in layers without putting the drain. Patient was given the IV broad spectrum cephalosporin one dose pre-operatively and followed BID dose till 48 hrs depending on the condition of the wound and patient.

Fig no 26 Skin Closure

Following parameters were recorded intra-operatively:

1. Total time of the surgery
2. Type of reduction: Closed/Joystick/Limited Open
3. Length of incision
4. Implant details
5. Radiation duration
6. Intraoperative complications
7. Quality of reduction

Aftertreatment:

- 1) Postoperatively, patient's pulse, blood pressure, respiration, temperature were monitored.
- 2) Foot elevation was given depending on blood pressure.
- 3) IV third generation Cephalosporin were administered 12 hourly for 3-5 days, and switched over to oral form till the 12th day post-operatively, i.e. until suture removal.
- 4) Analgesics were given as per patient compliance.
- 5) Blood transfusion was given depending on the requirement.
- 6) Suction drainage was removed after 48 hours, if it is inserted.
- 7) Dressing was done on 2nd, 5th and 8th postoperative day.
- 8) Sutures removed on 12th postoperative day.

PHYSIOTHERAPY

1. Patients were encouraged to sit in the bed after 24 hours after surgery.
2. Active isometric and isotonic quadriceps exercises were started from day 2.
3. Non weight bearing ambulation was started from 2nd week.
4. Partial weight bearing ambulation was started from 6th week.
5. Full weight bearing ambulation was started after radiological signs of union.

EVALUATION OF REDUCTION

Evaluation of the reduction was done using the following criteria on the post operative AP & Lat X-ray.

POSTOPERATIVE EVALUATION OF REDUCTION

According to Baumgaertner criteria modified by Fogagnolo et al.⁶⁷

I. Alignment

- i. Anteroposterior plane; normal collodiaphysal angle or slight valgus
- ii. Lateral plane: Angulation less than 20° degrees

II Displacement of main fragments

- i. More than 80% overlapping in both planes
- ii. Shortening less than 5mm

Result

Good	:	Meets both criteria
ACCEPTABLE	:	Meets only one criteria
POOR	:	Does not meet both criteria

Followup:

Followup at outpatient level at regular intervals at 6wks, 3months, and 6months for serial clinical and radiologic evaluation was done. If possible, further followup was done. At every visit, patient was assessed clinically regarding pain, limp, hip movements, walking ability, deformity and shortening.

Clinical assessment :

All patients were clinically assessed by using the Kyle's criteria⁶⁸.

Radiological assessment:

All patients were radiologically assessed for progression and time of union, fracture alignment and implant related complications.

KYLE'S CRITERIA⁶⁸

All patients after 6 months of follow up (after fracture union) were assessed clinically and functionally as per the following criteria. Patients were followed up for a minimum of 6 months and maximum of 1 year.

1. Excellent

- a. Fracture united.
- b. No pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Full range of motion at hip.
- e. No shortening.
- f. Patient able to sit crossed leg and squat.
- g. Independent gait.

2. Good

- a. Fracture united.
- b. Occasional pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Terminal restriction of hip movements.
- e. Shortening by half an inch.
- f. Patient able to sit crossed leg and squat.
- g. Use of cane back to full normal activity.

3. Fair

- a. Fracture united.
- b. Moderate hip pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Flexion restricted beyond eighty degrees.
- e. Noticeable limb shortening up to one inch.
- f. Patient not able to sit crossed leg.
- g. Patient walks with support of walker.
- h. Back to normal activities with minimal adjustments.

4. Poor

- a. Fractures not united.
- b. Pain even with slightest movement at hip or rest.
- c. Infection
- d. Range of movements at hip restricted, Flexion restricted beyond sixty degrees.
- e. Shortening more than one inch.
- f. Patient not able to sit crossed leg or squat.
- g. Patient cannot walk without walking aid.
- h. Normal activities not resumed.

CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL PHOTO GRAPHS

CASE 1

Pre operative X ray

Immediate post operative

Follow up at Six Months

Able to Sit and Squat

Active flexion

CASE2

Preopx-ray

Postopx-ray

Post op 3 months x-ray

Post op 6 months x-ray

Activeflexion

Abletosquat

CASE3

Preopx-ray

Postopx-ray

Postop6monthsx-ray

Sitting cross leg

Weight bearing on operative leg

Abletosquat

CASE4

Pre Operative Post Operative X Ray Follow up at 6 months

Flexion at Hip cross leg

SLRT

Sitting cross leg

INTRAOPERATIVECOMPLICATIONS

Greater Trochanter Splintering

Post operative complication

Z effect at 1.5 months

Union of fracture after revision surgery .

RESULTS AND OBSERVATION

The study involved 30 confirmed cases of Intertrochanteric fractures of either sex from Oct 2015-march 2017. All the cases were treated with Intramedullary fixation “Trochanteric femoral nail”. The analysis of the patient data, intraoperative data & postoperative outcome is as follows:

AGE

The study involved patients above 20 years of age. The age distribution was from 20 to 90 years. The average age was 58 years and the largest group of patients being from 60 to 70 years.

Table no 1 Age distribution

Age	No of patients	Percentage
20-30	2	6.6
30-40	2	6.6
40-50	5	16.6
50-60	4	13.3
60-70	9	30
70+	8	26.6
Total	30	100

Mean±SD= 58.13±15.3

Fig 27 Age Distribution

SEX

There were 22 males and 8 females in the study.

Table 2: Gender distribution

Gender	No of patients	Percentage
Male	22	73
Female	8	27
Total	30	100

Fig No 28 Gender Distribution

MODE OF INJURY

Domestic fall and road traffic accident were the mode of injury in all the patients. Most of the patients with domestic fall were older in age or had osteoporosis.

Table – 3 Mode of injury

Mode of Injury	No of patients	Percentage
Domestic fall	19	63.3
Road traffic accidents	11	36.7
Total	30	100

Fig 29 Mode of injury

SINGH'S INDEX

Table 4: Singh's Index Grades

Singh's Index Grades	No of patients	Percentage
I	0	0
II	1	3.3
III	13	43.3
IV	12	40.0
V	4	13.3
Total	30	100

Fig No. 30 Singh index of osteoporosis

FRACTURE PATTERNS

All the fractures were classified as per Orthopaedic Trauma Association (OTA) classification. In which 31A1 were considered stable fractures. 31A2 and 31A3 were unstable fractures.

Table no 5 Fracture pattern

Type of fracture	No of patients	Percentage
31A1	10	33.3
31A2	12	40
31A3	8	26.7
Total	30	100.0

Fig No.31 Fracture patterns

BLOOD LOSS AND BLOOD TRANSFUSION

Blood loss was counted intra operatively by number of mops used during the surgery. One mop equal to 50ml blood loss approximately. The average blood loss was 1.62 mops so 81ml (50-150ml). 4 patients required intra operative blood transfusion as their preoperative haemoglobin was less. None required blood transfusion post-operatively.

RADIATION EXPOSURE

The average radiation exposure via C-arm was 599.11 sec at 63 Gy rads.

OPERATING TIME

Average operating time was 55mins (32min-95min) after anesthesia.

ASSOCIATED MEDICAL PROBLEMS:

Four patients (13.3%) were suffering from Hypertension, two patients (6.7%) suffering from Diabetes mellitus and three patients (10%) were having both Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension.

Table 6: Associated medical problems

Associated medical problems	No of patients	Percentage
Diabetes Mellitus (DM)	2	6.7
Hypertension (HTN)	4	13.3
HTN & DM	3	10
NIL	21	70.0
Total	30	100.0

Fig No. 32 Associated Medical Problems

ASSOCIATED INJURIES :

One patients(3.3%) were having ipsilateral Distal end radius fracture and one patient (3.3%) from ipsilateralhumerus shaft fracture.

REDUCTION

Fracture was reduced anatomically by closed means. If that was not achieved then it was achieved by limited open reduction during surgery. Closed reduction was achieved in 27 patients (88.24%).

Table- 7 Reduction

Reduction	No. of patients	(%)
Closed	27	90
Limited open	3	10

Fig 33 Reduction of Fracture

COMPLICATIONS

Intra – Operative complication

In our study, we encountered certain complications intraoperatively. Most of these complications occurred :

- In three of our patient we had to do open reduction.
- In one cases we failed to achieve anatomical reduction .
- Greater trochanter splintering was seen in one patient which was healed well
Later.
- We had one case of fixation of fracture in varus angulation.
- We didn't face any Fracture of lateral cortex
- No Fracture displacement by nail insertion
- We did not found any jamming of instruments in our study .
- No Breakage of drill bit was seen in our study.

Table – 8 Intraoperative complications

Sl . no	Complications	No of patients
1)	Difficulty in achieving closed reduction	3(10%)
2)	failed to achieve anatomical reduction	1(3.3%)
3)	Failed to put derotation screw	0
4)	difficulty in distal locking in 0 patients	0
5)	fixation of fracture in varus angulation	1(3.3%)
6)	Fracture of lateral cortex	0 (0%)
7)	Jamming of Instruments	1(3.3%)
8)	Greater trochanter splintering	1(3.3%)

Fig 34 Intraoperative Complication

Post operative complication:

Early :

- Shortening of 2mm is seen in 2patient.
- No Rotation deformity seen.
- In two patient Superficialinfection was seen.
- No cases of Deep infection.
- None suffered from Bed sores.
- No Mortality.

Table 9 Early post op complication

Sl .no	complication	No of patients
1	Shortening	2 (3%)
2	Rotation deformity	0 (0%)
3	Superficial infection	2 (6.7%)
4	Deep infection	0 (0%)
5	Bed sores	0
6	Mortality	0 (0%)

Late complications:

1.Implant failure

In 1 case the 'Z' - effect of implant failure was seen. Early weight bearing, improper screw placement, stress risers were the causes of this failure.

2.Non - Union

There were no cases of non-union in my study.

3 .VarusMal-Union.

Two patients hadVarus Mal union in my study

Table 10: Delayed complications

Delayed complications	No of patients	Percentage
NIL	25	83.3
Shortening	2	6.7
VM,	2	6.7
Z-EFFECT	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Fig 35 Post operative Complications

HOSPITAL STAY

The average hospital stay was 14.11 (10- 26) days from date of admission to date of discharge. It varied in patients due to factors like availability of operation theatre and comorbid conditions of the patients.

CRITERIA FOR EVALUATION AND RESULTS [KYLE'S

criteria]⁶⁸

All the patients after union of fracture or after 6 months were grouped and the anatomical and functional results evaluated as follows.

1. Excellent

- a. Fracture united.
- b. No pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Full range of motion at hip.
- e. No shortening.
- f. Patient able to sit crossed leg and squat.
- g. Independent gait.

2. Good

- a. Fracture united.
- b. Occasional pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Terminal restriction of hip movements.
- e. Shortening by half an inch.
- f. Patient able to sit crossed leg and squat.
- g. Use of cane back to full normal activity.

3. Fair

- a. Fracture united.
- b. Moderate hip pain.
- c. No infection.
- d. Flexion restricted beyond eighty degrees.

- e. Noticeable limb shortening up to one inch.
- f. Patient not able to sit crossed leg.
- g. Patient walks with support of walker.
- h. Back to normal activities with minimal adjustments.

4. Poor

- a. Fractures not united.
- b. Pain even with slightest movement at hip or rest.
- c. Infection
- d. Range of movements at hip restricted, Flexion restricted beyond sixty degrees.
- e. Shortening more than one inch.
- f. Patient not able to sit crossed leg or squat.
- g. Patient cannot walk without walking aid.
- h. Normal activities not resumed.

RESULTS ACCORDING TO KYLE'S CRITERIA

There were 30 confirmed cases of intertrochanteric fractures .

Table 11: Results according to Kyle's Criteria

Results	No of patients	Percentage
Excellent	11	36.7
Good	13	43.3
Fair	5	16.7
Poor	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Fig 36 Results according to Kyle's criteria

6. DISCUSSION

The successful treatment of Intertrochanteric fractures depends on many factors like⁶⁹:

- Age of the patient
- Patients general health
- Time from fracture to treatment
- The adequacy of treatment
- Concurrent medical illness
- Stability of the fixation

At present it is generally believed that all Intertrochanteric fractures should be internally fixed to reduce the morbidity and the mortality of the patient. But the appropriate method and the ideal implant by which to fix the Intertrochanteric fracture is still in a debate. Because each method having its own advantages and the disadvantages.

In the present study 30 patients of Intertrochanteric fractures were studied.

In our study the average age was 58 years which was comparable to Indian as well as western authors with similar study.

We had an 22 male patients and 8 female patients, this resembles many Indian studies. The most common mode of injury in our study was domestic fall 63.7%, which is comparable to most of the Indian studies. This was also affected by the age as the older the patient are more likely getting the fracture by domestic falls.

In our study 33% were stable fracture pattern and 67% were unstable.

Osteoporosis was measured by the Singh's index. More osteoporosis was present in the older patient and post menopausal females. In our study 43% had a grade – III osteoporosis. The average intra operative blood loss was very minimal. The average was 81ml and it was more in patients who required a limited open

reduction. Only four (11.%) of our patients required intra or post operative transfusion. But many of them had very low preoperative haemoglobin. Radiation exposure was calculated in seconds, it was 599.11 seconds by the C-arm. Stable fractures required less exposure than the unstable fractures. This is far below the toxic levels of the radiation.

The average operating time was 55 mins from the incision to closure. We had a longer operating time in the beginning which reduced greatly in the later part of the study. This signifies the learning curve of the Trochanteric femoral nailing.

The average hospital stay was 14 days. It was more in patients with co-morbid conditions and complications with highest being 22 days.

Total Post operative complications in our study were 17%. We had “Z - effect” in 3.3% of patients which was mostly due to improper placement of the hip screw or cervical screw and early mobilization of the patients. All these patients required revision with a different sizes screws and fracture healed well after revision. This was comparable to W.M.Gadegoneetal³³ it was slightly lower than their study. There was no case of non-union. 3% of our patients had greater trochanter splintering while inserting the nail but no other intervention was required and all the fractures healed well.

Infection was present in 6.7% of the patient it was superficial which was treated with antibiotics and dressing in the ward, none required debridement or revision and healed well.

At the follow up there was no complaint of anterior thigh pain or the fracture of the femoral shaft at the tip of the nail.

Results were evaluated by Kyle’s criteria⁶⁴ in our series we had 36.7% excellent, 43.3% good, 16.7 % fair and 3.3% poor results. It was similar to

W.M.Gadegone et al³³ & Pavelka et al²⁶ that the use of TFN may have a positive effect on the speed at which walking is restored.

In the series of 295 patients with trochanteric fractures treated with TFN by Domingo et al⁶⁹ the average age of the patient was 80 years, which possibly accounted for 27% of the patients developed complications in the immediate postoperative period. The success of Trochanter femoral nail depended on good surgical technique, proper instrumentation and good C-arm visualization. All the patients were operated on fracture table. We found following advantages

- Reduction with traction is easier.
- Less assistance is required.
- Manipulation of the patient is reduced to minimum.
- Trauma to patient is decreased.
- Better use of C-arm with better visibility.

Placement of the patient on the fracture table is important, for better access to the greater trochanter the upper body is abducted away 10-15°. Position of the C-arm should be such that proximal femur is seen properly in AP and lateral view.

The anatomical reduction and secure fixation of the patient on the operating table are absolutely vital for easy handling and good surgical result. If reduction was not achieved by traction and manipulation then nail reduction was done, in which nail was introduced in the proximal fragment and reduction was tried by rotational movements and compression by the nail. If still reduction was a problem, then it was achieved by limited open reduction at the fracture site. In our study 10 % patients required limited open reduction which was higher than Christian Boldin et al as they required in 9%⁷. The entry point of the nail was taken on the tip or the lateral part of

the greater trochanter. As the nail has 6° of valgus angle medial entry point cause more distraction of the fracture.

The hip pin is inserted 5mm away from the subchondral bone in the lower half in the AP view and center on the neck in the lateral view. The cervical pin is placed parallel to the hip pin in AP view and overlapping it in the lateral view. It should be 10mm shorter than the hip pin from the subchondral bone. This ensures that the cervical screw will not take the weight load but only fulfill the anti-rotational function. Failure to do this leads to the “Z - effect”. In which the cervical pin backs out and the hip pin pierces the joint or the vice-versa. Distal locking was done with the interlocking bolt and both static and dynamic holes were locked in all the nails in our study.

In our study one of the important factor was the cost of the implant as Trochanteric femoral nail is costly than the dynamic hip screw, but at the end it didn't cause much of the difference as:

- Less operative time thus reducing the cost
- No or less need of transfusion of blood
- Post operative antibiotics were used less thus reducing the cost of the drugs
- Less hospital stay
- Early return to daily activities.

Dynamic hip screw introduced by clawson in 1964 remains the implant of choice due to its favourable results and low rate of complications. It provides control compression at the fracture site. Its use has been supported by its biomechanical properties which have been assumed to improve the healing of the fracture²³.

But Dynamic hip screw requires a relatively larger exposure, more tissue trauma and anatomical reduction. All these increase the morbidity, probability of infection

and significant blood loss. It also causes varus collapse leading to shortening and inability of the implant to survive until the fracture union.

The plate and screw device will weaken the bone mechanically. The common causes of fixation failure are instability of the fractures, osteoporosis, lack of anatomical reduction, failure of fixation device and incorrect placement of the screw.⁷⁰

We found Trochanteric femoral nail to be more useful in unstable and reverse oblique patterns due to the fact that it has better axial telescoping and rotational stability. It has shown to be more biomechanically stronger because they can withstand higher static and several fold higher cyclical loading than dynamic hip screw. So the fracture heals without the primary restoration of the medial support. The implant compensates for the function of the medial column.²⁶

The gamma nail is associated with specific complications like anterior thigh pain, fracture at the tip of the nail. But trochantric femoral nail has smaller diameter at the tip which reduces the stress concentration at the tip.

Its position is near to the weight bearing axis so the stress generated on the implant is negligible. Trochanteric femoral nail also acts as a buttress in preventing the medialization of the shaft. The entry point of the Trochanteric femoral nail is at the tip of the greater trochanter so it reduces the damage to the hip abductors⁷¹ unlike the nails which have entry through piriformis fossa⁷¹. The hip screw and the anti rotation cervical screw of the Trochanteric femoral nail adequately compress the fracture, leaving between them adequate bone block for further revision should the need arise.

CONCLUSION

Literature suggests that Dynamic hip screw is the Gold standard for treatment of stable type of intertrochanteric fractures as well as unstable types. According to our study and use of Trochanteric femoral nail in Intertrochanteric fractures we can say that:

Trochanteric Femoral Nail can be considered the most judicious and rational method of treating intertrochanteric fractures , especially the unstable and reverse oblique type.

The data was assessed, analyzed, evaluated and the following conclusions were made:

- Peritrochanteric fracture of the femur is common in the elderly, due to osteoporosis and in young due to high velocity trauma.
- It can be used in all configurations of proximal femoral fractures.
- It is a closed method thus preserves the fracture hematoma and yields early healing and early union.
- It can be used with equally good results in all grades of osteoporosis.
- It is a quick procedure with a small incision and with significantly less amount of blood loss.
- It gives good results even with non-anatomical reduction.
- Hip screw and cervical screw placement is important. They have to be parallel in AP and overlapping in lateral. Cervical screw should 10mm shorter than hip screw to avoid the “Z - effect”.
- Nail entry is on the tip of the greater trochanter or lateral to it as medial entry will cause the distraction.
- Complications were minimal and comparable with other fracture systems. But Trochanteric femoral nailing requires a higher surgical skill, good

fracture table, good instrumentation and good C-arm control. It has a steep learning curve.

- Post-operatively early mobilization can be begun as the fixation is rigid and because of the implant design
- With the experience gained from each case the operative time, radiation exposure, blood loss and intraoperative complications can be reduced drastically.

Thus we can conclude that the TROCHANTERIC FEMORAL NAIL is after proper training and technique a safe and easy implant option for treatment of complex intertrochanteric fractures.

SUMMARY

Intertrochanteric femoral fractures are of intense interest globally. Intertrochanteric fracture is a leading cause of hospital admissions in elderly people. The number of such admissions is on a raise because of increasing life span, sedentary habits and increased road traffic accidents.

Conservative methods of treatment results in malunion with shortening and limitation of hip movement as well as complications of prolonged immobilization like bed sores, deep vein thrombosis and respiratory infections.

This study is done to analyze the surgical management of Intertrochanteric fractures using Trochanteric Femoral Nail.

In our series of 30 cases there were 22 male and 8 female, maximum age of 90 yrs and minimum age of 20 yrs, most of the patients were between 60 to 70 yrs. Mean age of 58 yrs. 63.3% of cases were admitted due to Domestic fall and 36.7% due to road traffic accidents with common predominance of both sides. AO Type 31A2 fracture accounted for 40 % of cases. Mean duration of hospital stay is 14 days and mean time of full weight bearing is 6 wks. Out of 30 cases 1 case expired after 7 months due to non orthopaedic cause and 1 cases were lost to follow up. Good to excellent results are seen in 81% cases, Fair in 16%, 3% case with poor results.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1) David Tanner A, MasitaKloseck, Richard Gilly G, Bert Chesworth, Jason Gilliland. Hip Fracture Type In Men And Women Change Differently With Age. BMC Geriatr. March 2010; 10:12.
- 2) Babulkar S.S. Management of trochanteric fractures .Indian J Orthop 2006; 40:210-8.
- 3) Kenneth J Koval,Robert V. Canter , Rockwood and Greens fracture in Adults, Philadelphia: Lippincott William and Wilkins,2006:6th Edition:Page1794-1824
- 4) Campbell's operative orthopedics; Philadelphia: Mosby Elsevier; 2008.Vol 3; 11th edition: 3239-3256.
- 5) Meislin RJ, Zuckerman JD, Kummer FJ, et al. A biomechanical evaluation of the gamma nail. J Bone Joint Surg.1998; 70-A:239.
- 6) Anchal Kumar. Femoral neck geometry and rationale of placement of the proximal femoral nail and its relation with fracture risk in the Indian population review of 120 cases. 2010: Gulmohar Hospital, Ronchi.
- 7) Whitman R. A new method of treatment for fractures of the neck of the femur, together with remarks on coxavara. Ann Surg 1902;36:746
- 8) HendersonM.Hipfracturetreatment.ProcStaffMeetMayoClin1936;2:573.
- 9) HenryM.Lateralintroductionofthescrew-boltinintracapsularfractureofthe hip.JBoneJointSurgAm1938;20(2):400-404.
- 10) Lippmann R.Experiences withthecorkscrew bolt.JBone Joint SurgAm
- 11) Thornton L.The treatment oftrochanteric fractures ofthefemur:twonew methods.PiedmontHosp1937;10:21-27.

- 12) Barros JW, Ferreira CD, Freitas AA, Farah S. External fixation of intertrochanteric fractures of the femur. *Int Orthop* 1995;19(4):217-219.
- 13) Gotfried Y, Frish E, Mendes DG, et al. Intertrochanteric fractures in high-risk geriatric patients treated by external fixation. *Orthopedics* 1985;8(6):769-774.
- 14) Krikler SJ. External fixation in unstable intertrochanteric fractures of femur. *Injury* 1996;27(10):756.
- 15) Simmermacher RKJ, Bosch AM, VanderWerken C. The AO/ASIF-Proximal femoral nail: a new device for the treatment of unstable proximal femoral fractures. *Injury* 1999;30:327-32.
- 16) Gotfried Y, Cohen B, Rotem A. Biomechanical evaluation of the percutaneous compression plating system for hip fractures. *J Orthop Trauma* 2002;16(9):644-650.
- 17) Iori Takigami, Kazu Matsumoto et al. Treatment of Trochanteric Fractures with the PFNA (Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation) Nail System-Report of Early Results. *Bulletin of the NYU Hospital for Joint Diseases* 2008; 66 (4):276-9.
- 18) Gadegone WM, Salphale YS. Short Proximal Femoral Nail Fixation for trochanteric Fractures *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong)*. 2010 Apr;18(1):39-44.
- 19) Bucholz RW, Heckman JD, Koval KJ, Zukerman JD. *Rockwood and Green's fractures in adults*. 6th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2005.
- 20) GS Kulkarni, Rajiv Limaye, Milind Kulkarni, Sunil Kulkarni. Current Concept review Intertrochanteric fractures. *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics* 2006 Jan; 40(1):16-23.

- 21) Simmermacher RKJ, Bosch AM, Van der Werken C. The AO/ASIF- Proximal femoral nail: a new device for the treatment of unstable proximal femoral fractures. *Injury* 1999; 30: 327-32.
- 22) Christian Boldin, Franz J. Seibert, Florian Fankhauser, Gerolf Peicha, Wolfgang Grechenig, et al. Proximal femoral nail (PFN) – A minimal invasive treatment of unstable proximal femoral fracture. *Acta Orthopaedica* 2003 Feb; 74(1): 53-8.
- 23) Pajarinen J, Lindahl J, Michelsson O, Savolainen V, Hirvensalo E. Pertrochanteric Femoral Fractures Treated With a Dynamic Hip Screw or a Proximal Femoral Nail. A Randomized Study Comparing Post-Operative Rehabilitation. *The Journal of Joint and Bone Surgery (Br)*. Jan 2005; 87 (1):76-81.
- 24) Klinger HM, Baums MH, Eckert M, Neugebauer R. A comparative study of unstable per and intertrochanteric femoral fractures treated with dynamic hip screw (DHS) and trochanteric press plate Vs proximal femoral nail (PFN). *ZentralblChir*. 2005 Aug; 130(4): 301-6.
- 25) Reska M., Veverkova L., Divis P., Konecny J. Proximal femoral nail (PFN)- A new stage in the therapy of extra capsular femoral fractures. *SCRIPTA MEDICA (BRNO)* 2006 June; 79(2): 115-22.
- 26) Pavelka T, Houcek P, Linhart M, Matejka J. Osteosynthesis of hip and femoral shaft fractures using the PFN-long. *Acta Chir Orthop Traumatol Cech*. 2007 Apr; 74(2):91-8.
- 27) W. M. Gadegone, Y. S. Salphale. Proximal femoral nail – an analysis of 100 cases of proximal femoral fractures with an average follow up of 1 year. *International Orthopaedics* 2007 June; 31(3): 403-8.

- 28) Thesis present to the University of Seychelles, American institute of medicine by Dr. Ramesh Krishna k. title . A Comparative prospective study of Dynamic hip screw and proximal femoral nail in the treatment of Inter-trochanteric fracture study presented in 2009.
- 29) MP Anjum and N Hussain .Treatment of intertrochanteric femoral fractures with a proximal femoral nail (PFN): a short follow up. Nepal Med Coll J 2009; 11(4): 229-231.
- 30) Egol KA, Chang EY, Cvitkovic J, Kummer FJ, Koval KJ. Mismatch of current intramedullary nails with the anterior bow of the femur. J Orthop Trauma 2004; 18: 410–5.
- 31) Siwach RC, Dahiya S. Anthropometric study of proximal femur geometry and its clinical application. Indian J Orthop 2003; 37: 247–51.
- 32) Leung KS, Chen CM, So WS, Sato K, Lai CH, Machaisavariya B, et al. Multicenter trial of modified Gamma nail in East Asia. Clin Orthop Relat Res 1996; 323: 146–54.
- 33) Gadegone W M, Salphale Y S, Proximal femoral nail- An analysis of 100 cases of proximal fractures with in an average follow up of 1 year. International Orthopedics. Jun 2006; 31: 403-408.
- 34) Mandal S, Kundu S, Hyam A . Short-term evaluation of results of trochanteric femoral nailing (TFN) “in comminuted unstable trochanteric hip fractures”. International Journal of Conference Proceedings 2015; (2015): 74.
- 35) David G Lavelle , Campbell’s operative orthopaedics , 11th edition , library of congress publishing data , 2008 . p3239-62 , vol3.

- 36) Bucholz RW, Heckman JD, Koval KJ, Zukerman JD. Rockwood and Green's fractures in adults. 6th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2005.
- 37) Koval KJ, Zuckerman JD. Hip fractures: a practical guide to management. New York: Springer-verlag; 2000.
- 38) Soames RW, Salmous S, Bannister LH, Berry MM, Dyson M. Gray's anatomy. 38th ed. New York: Churchill Livingstone; 1995: 678-89.
- 39) Wilson C, Hayes, Van C. Basic orthopaedic biomechanics. 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 1997.
- 40) Rydell N. Biomechanics of hip joint. CORR 1973; 6: 15.
- 41) Wilson C, Hayes, Van C. Basic orthopaedic biomechanics. 2nd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 1997.
- 42) Rydell N. Biomechanics of hip joint. CORR 1973; 6: 15
- 43) Horn SR, Wang M. The mechanism traumatic anatomy and treatment of intertrochanteric fracture of the femur. Br J Surg. 1964; 51: 234-45.
- 44) Bong MR, Datel V et al. The comparison of sliding hip screw with a trochanteric plate to an intramedullary hip screw for unstable intertrochanteric fractures. J Orthop Trauma 2004; 50 (4): 791-94.
- 45) Haidukewych GJ, Israel TA, Berry DJ. Reverse oblique fracture of the intertrochanteric region of the femur. J Bone Joint Surg Am 2001; 83 A: 643-50.
- 46) Sadowski C, Lubbeke M, Sudan M, Riand N, Stern R, Hoffmeyer P. Treatment of reverse oblique and transverse inter-trochanteric fractures with the use of an intramedullary nail or a 95 degree plate. J Bone Joint Surg Am 2002; 84 A: 372.

- 47) Evans E. The treatment of intertrochanteric fractures of the femur. *J Bone Joint Surg Br* 1949; 31: 190-203.
- 48) Boyd HB, Griffin LL. Classification and treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. *Arch Surg* 1949; 58: 853-66.
- 49) Kyle RF, Gustilo RB, Premer RF. Analysis of six hundred and twenty two cases of intertrochanteric fractures of the femur. *J Bone Joint Surg Am* 1979; 61: 216-21.
- 50) Tronzo RG. Special considerations in management of intertrochanteric fractures. *Clin Orthop North Am* 1974; 5: 571-83.
- 51) Scott JC. Treatment of trochanteric fractures. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1949; 33 B: 508.
- 52) Frew JFM. Conservative treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1972; 54 B: 746.
- 53) Jensen JS. Classification of trochanteric fractures. *Acta Orthop Scand* 1980; 51:803-10.
- 54) Hafner RMV. Trochanteric fractures of femur. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1951; 32 B: 513.
- 55) Messie WK. Fractures of the hip. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1964; 46 A: 658.
- 56) Müller ME, Allgöwer M, Schneider R, Willenegger H. Manual of internal fixation techniques recommended by the AO/ASIF group. 3rd ed. Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1991.
- 57) Jensen JS. Classification of trochanteric fractures. *Acta Orthop Scand* 1980; 51:803-10.

- 58) GS Kulkarni, Rajiv Limaye, Milind Kulkarni, Sunil Kulkarni. Current Concept review Intertrochanteric fractures. Indian Journal of Orthopaedics 2006 Jan; 40(1):16-23.
- 59) Hafner RMV. Trochanteric fractures of femur. J Bone Joint Surg 1951; 32 B: 513.
- 60) Rosenblum SF, Zuckerman JD, Kummer FJ, Tam bs. A biomechanical evaluation of the gamma nail. J Bone Joint Surg Br 1992; 74: 352-57.
- 61) Ely L Steinberg, Nehemia Blumberg, Shmuel Dekel. The fixation proximal femur nailing system: biomechanical properties of the nail and a cadaveric study. J of Biomechanics 2005; 38: 63-8.
- 62) Loch DA, Kyle RF. The forces required to slide a 2nd generation intramedullary nail. J Bone Joint Surg Am 1998: 1626-31.
- 63) Lindsey RW, Teal P, Probe RA, Rhodas D et al. Early experience with a gamma nail for peritrochanteric fractures of the proximal femur. J Orthop Trauma 1991; 71: 1649-58.
- 64) Kyle RF, Wright TM, Burstein AH. Biomechanical analysis of the sliding characteristics of compression hip screw. J Bone Joint Surg Am 1980; 62: 1308-14.
- 65) Gundle R, Gargan MF, Simpson AHRW. How to minimize failures of fixation of unstable intertrochanteric fractures. Injury 1995; 26: 611-14.
- 66) Spivak JM, Zuckerman JD, Kummer FJ. Fatigue failure of sliding hip screw in hip fractures a report of three cases. J Orthop Trauma 1991; 3: 325-31.
- 67) Baumgaertner MR, Curtin SL, Lindskog DM, Keggi J. The value of the tip-apex distance in predicting failure of fixation of peritrochanteric fractures of the hip. J Bone Joint Surg Am 1995; 77: 1058-64.

- 68) Kyle RF, Wright TM, Burstein AH. Biomechanical analysis of the sliding characteristics of compression hip screw. *J Bone Joint Surg Am* 1980; 62: 1308-14.
- 69) Domingo LJ, Cecilia D, Herrera A, Resines C. Trochanteric fractures treated with a proximal femoral nail. *IntOrthop* 2001; 25: 298-301.
- 70) Curtis MJ, Jinnh RH, Wilson V, Cunningham BW. Proximal femoral fractures; a biomechanical study to compare extramedullary and intramedullary fixation. *Injury* 1994; 25: 99-104.
- 71) Ansari Moein CM, Verhofstad MHJ, Bleys RLAW, Werken C vander. Soft tissue injury related to the choice of entry point in ante grade femoral nailing; piriform fossa or greater trochanter tip. *Injury* 2005; 36: 1337-42.

ANNEXURES
ETHICAL CERTIFICATE

PROFORMA

CASE NO

NAME

AGE/SEX

I.P. NO

DATE OF ADMISSION

DATE OF SURGERY

DATE OF DISCHARGE

OCCUPATION

ADDRESS

1) COMPLAINTS

2) HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS:

- a) Duration between the injury and first visit
- b) Symptoms — Swelling
Pain
Loss of function

3) MODE OF INJURY

- a) Fall
- b) Blunt trauma
- c) Vehicular accidents

4) GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Pulse:

B.P:

5) SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION:

Respiratory system —
Cardiovascular system —
Per abdomen —
Central nervous system

6) LOCAL EXAMINATION:

INSPECTION

- a) Deformity and Attitude
- b) Shortening

- c) Swelling
- d) Skin
- e) Wounds if any
- f) Other injuries or fractures if any

Right

Left

7) MEASUREMENTS

PALPATION

- a) Tenderness
- b) Pain elicited on manipulation
- c) Local bony irregularity
- d) Swelling
- e) Abnormal mobility
- f) Crepitus/grating of fragments
- a) Absence of transmitted movements
- h) Wounds Right or Left

Measurements

- | | | |
|----------|---|--|
| Apparent | - | xiphisternum to medial malleolus |
| Real | - | Anterior superior iliac spine to Medial malleolus |
| | - | Anterior superior iliac spine to Medial joint line |
| | - | Medial joint line to medial malleolus |

Bryants Triangle:

Nelaton's line:

MANAGEMENT: INVESTIGATIONS:

X-ray of antero-posterior view of pelvis with both hips and lateral view of affected hip

will be taken.

BLOOD:

Hb%

TC

DC

ESR

Blood grouping Rh typing

URINE

Albumin

Sugar

BLOOD SUGAR RANDOM

BLOOD UREA

SERUM CREATININE

ECG in elderly

CHEST X RAY - PA view

MANAGEMENT:

- Type of fixation used
- Stability of the operating- table
- Intra operative complications if any

POST OPERATIVE MANAGEMENT:

- **Mobilization**
 - Date of mobilization of hip
 - Date of patient sitting
 - Date of weight bearing
- **Wound healing, and suture removal**
- **Complications**
 - Infection
 - Change in position of implant
 - Loss of reduction
 - Nerve palsy
- **Date of discharge**

CONDITION AT DISCHARGE

- **Clinical**
 - Shortening if any
 - Complications if any

- Deformity
 - Flexion
 - Adduction
 - Rotational
- Range of movements
 - Active
 - Passive
 - Flexion
 - Adduction
 - Abduction
 - Internal rotation
 - External rotation

Follow up:

(4-6 weeks)

- Clinical
 - Patient complaints
 - Pain
 - Limp
 - Any other
 - Deformity
 - Flexion
 - Adduction/ Abduction
 - Rotational
 - Movements
 - Flexion
 - Adduction
 - Abduction
 - Rotation

- Quadriceps
 - o Wasting
 - o Power

- Shortening
 - Radiological
 - Position of the in-implant
 - Position of fragments
 - o Follow up
 - (8to 10 weeks)
 - Clinical
 - Patient complaints
 - Pain
 - Limp
 - Any other
 - Deformity
 - Flexion
 - Adduction / Abduction
 - Rotational

- Movements

Active	Passive
--------	---------

Movements

- Flexion
- Adduction
- Abduction
- Rotation
- Squatting
- Easy

- Difficult
- Not possible

Quadriceps

- Wasting
- Power
- Shortening compensation if any
- Walking distance
 - Free
 - Painless
 - Pain mild
 - Pain severe
- **With aid**
 - Pain less
 - Pain mild
 - Pain severe
-
- **Radiological**
 - Fracture union and date
 - Position of implant
 - Position of fragments

Follow up

(20 to 24 weeks)

➤ **Clinical**

- Patient complaints
 - Pain

- Limp
- Any other
- Deformity
 - Flexion
 - Adduction / Abduction
 - Rotational

Movements	Active	Passive
• Flexion		
• Adduction		
• Abduction		
• Rotation		
• Squatting		
	○ Easy	
	○ Difficult	
	○ Not possible	

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF RESEARCH : **A PROSPECTIVE STUDY OF
FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF
INTERTROCHANTERIC
FRACTURES TREATED WITH
TROCHANTERIC FEMORAL
NAIL.**

Principle Investigator :

P.G. Guide Name :

M.S ORTHOPAEDICS
PROFESSOR AND HOD

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her.

I, the undersigned, _____ , S/O D/O W/O _____,
aged ____years, ordinarily resident of _____ do hereby state/declare that Dr
_____ College Hospital and Research Centre has
examined me thoroughly on _____ at _____ (place) and it has
been explained to me in my own language that I am suffering from
_____ disease (condition) and this disease/condition mimic following
diseases.

Further _____informed me that he/she is conducting dissertation/research titled “A Prospective Study Of Functional Outcome Of Intertrochanteric FracturesTreated With Trochanteric Femoral Nail”under the guidance of _____requesting my participation in the study. Apart from routine treatment procedure, the pre-operative, operative, post-operative and follow-up observations will be utilized for the study as reference data.

Doctor has also informed me that during conduct of this procedure like adverse results may be encountered. Among the above complications most of them are treatable but are not anticipated hence there is chance of aggravation of my condition and in rare circumstances it may prove fatal in spite of anticipated diagnosis and best treatment made available. Further Doctor has informed me that my participation in this study help in evaluation of the results of the study which is useful reference to treatment of other similar cases in near future, and also I may be benefited in getting relieved of suffering or cure of the disease I am suffering.

The Doctor has also informed me that information given by me, observations made/ photographs/ video graphs taken upon me by the investigator will be kept secret and not assessed by the person other than me or my legal hirer except for academic purposes.

The Doctor did inform me that though my participation is purely voluntary, based on information given by me, I can ask any clarification during the course of treatment / study related to diagnosis, procedure of treatment, result of treatment or prognosis. At the same time I have been informed that I can withdraw from my participation in this study at any time if I want or the investigator can terminate me

from the study at any time from the study but not the procedure of treatment and follow-up unless I request to be discharged.

After understanding the nature of dissertation or research, diagnosis made, mode of treatment, I the undersigned Shri/Smt _____ under my full conscious state of mind agree to participate in the said research/dissertation.

Signature of patient:

Signature of doctor:

Witness: 1.

2.

Date:

Place

Key to master chart

1. Name :
2. IP. No : Hospital number of the patients
3. Sex : Sex of the patient
4. D.O.S: Date of surgery
5. MOI : Mode of the injury
 - a. Domestic fall =D
 - b. Road traffic accidents =R
 - c. Other =O
6. SI : Singh's Index Grade I,II,III ,IV, V and VI
7. Side : Side of the injury Lt = Left , Rt = Right
8. Type of # : Type of fracture according to the AO Classification
 - a. A1=31A1.
 - b. A2=31A2.
 - c. A3=31A3.
9. Ass Med problems : Associated medical problems.
 - a. DM : Diabetes Mellitus.
 - b. HTN : Hypertension.
10. Ass injuries : Associated injuries.
 - a. D R # : Distal end radius fracture.
 - b. Humerus# :Humerus fracture.
11. BL : Blood Loss occurred during surgery , according to number of mops used 1 mop= 50ml blood loss, 2 mops =100ml blood loss and 3 mops = 150 ml
12. RD : Radiaton by C-Arm at 63 gyrads in seconds
13. ImmCompl: Immediate complication

- a. OR : Open reduction
- b. Jamm: Jamming.
- c. VA :Varus angulation.
- d. DL : Failure to insert distal screw

14. D Compl : Delayed complication.

- a. SI : Superficial infection.
- b. BS : Bed sore.
- c. IF : Implant failure.
- d. GTS : Greater trochanter splintering.
- e. Short : Shortening
- f. MU : Malunion

15. HS : Duration of the hospital stay in days.

16. Result: Result according to Kyle's Criteria.

- a. Excellent : E.
- b. Good : G.
- c. Fair : F.
- d. Poor : P

MASTER CHART

Sl no	Name	IP NO	Age	Sex	D/O/S	MOI	SI	SIDE	Type of #	Med Problems	Ass Injuries	ImmComp.	D compl	HS	Result
1	AMOGH	37247	50	M	10\10\2015	D	IV	RT	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	13	E
2	NINGAMMA	32630	68	F	17\10\2015	R	V	Rt	31A2	HTN	NIL	NIL	NIL	20	E
3	SIDDAMMA	34636	67	F	30\10\2015	R	III	RT	31A3	NIL	NIL	OR	NIL	14	F
4	HANAMANTH	31099	65	M	12\10\2015	R	III	Rt	31A1	DM	NIL	NIL	SI	12	E
5	RAMACHANDRA	38780	80	M	05\12\2015	D	III	Lt	31A3	HTN	NIL	VA	VM,SHR	15	G
6	MAHADEV	35586	50	M	05\11\2015	R	IV	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	13	E
7	CHANDRABAGA	36219	45	F	09\11\2015	D	V	Lt	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	13	E
8	MALAPPA	36827	45	M	19\11\2015	D	IV	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	GTS	NIL	14	E
9	BASAPPA	38411	60	M	07\12\2015	R	IV	Lt	31A1	HTN/DM	NIL	NIL	NIL	20	G
10	PARUBAI	38987	60	F	15\12\2015	R	III	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	Z-EFFECT	15	F
11	SRIKANTH	3288	64	M	04\02\2016	D	III	Lt	31A2	NIL	Humerus shaft #	OR	NIL	13	G
12	CHANDSAB MULLA	9123	51	M	29\03\2016	D	II	Rt	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	22	G
13	IRAPPA TALEWAD	10233	80	M	04\04\2016	D	IV	Rt	31A3	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	12	F
14	GANGAMMA	13835	62	F	3\04\2016	D	IV	Rt	31A1	HTN	NIL	jam	NIL	12	E
15	SATISH	16897	50	M	24/5/2016	D	IV	Lt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	12	G
16	GOPAL RATHOD	22076	45	M	7/7/2016	R	IV	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	10	G
17	REVUTAPPA	22242	49	M	8/7/2016	D	IV	Rt	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	nil	11	E
18	SEETABAI	23033	70	F	19/7/2016	R	III	Lt	31A3	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	12	F
19	SIDDAPPA	21611	78	M	9/7/2016	D	III	Rt	31A2	HTN,DM	NIL	NIL	SI	17	F

20	HANUMANTHARAYA	21987	65	M	9/7/2016	D	III	Lt.	31A3	HTN	D R #	OR	NIL	12	G
21	KAMALABAI	26555	65	F	30/7/2016	D	IV	Rt	31A3	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	10	G
22	SUDHAKAR	27375	28	M	27/8/2016	D	V	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	12	G
23	SAVALAGAPPA	28380	83	M	6/9/2016	R	III	Lt	31A3	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	11	G
24	RAMACHANDRA	34255	70	M	20/10/2016	D	III	Lt	31A2	DM	NIL	NIL	VM,SHR	18	P
25	CHAYA	33907	28	F	14/10/2016	R	V	Lt	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	16	E
26	GANESH	33807	36	M	27/10/2016	D	IV	Lt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	13	G
27	JPTEPPA	34916	70	M	5/11/2016	D	III	Lt	31A1	DM,HTN	NIL	NIL	NIL	17	G
28	NINGAPPA	39386	75	M	3/12/2016	D	III	Lt	31A3	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	16	G
29	BASAYYA	242	48	M	5/1/2017	R	III	Rt	31A1	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	10	E
30	RAJESH JAIN	1243	37	M	28/1/2017	D	IV	Rt	31A2	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	13	E